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A Survey on Distributed Denial of Service Attack Mitigation for 5G and Beyond

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ABSTRACT The introduction of 6G networks is expected to significantly change the threat landscape related to Distributed Denial of Service (DDoS) attacks, requiring robust detection and mitigation measures. This paper methodologically classifies and evaluates the growing collection of research efforts focusing on detection and protection mechanisms against DDoS attacks in 5G and beyond networks. The survey covers various methods used in the scientific literature and categorizes DDoS mitigation efforts into two main areas: DDoS detection and DDoS defense. It thoroughly analyzes each approach, highlighting its benefits, limitations, and effectiveness in mitigating DDoS attacks against B5G. This survey also discusses the experimental environments and data sets being used for each work by comparing them. Finally, we provide insights and directions for future research and development efforts to protect B5G networks against DDoS threats. Our results highlight gaps in current methods, including problems such as the lack of real-time testbed implementations and the inability to reproduce the results of experiments. In addition, we suggest future research directions that emphasize quantum-resistant solutions and scalable architectures for next-generation networks. This work aims to guide researchers and practitioners in developing robust and adaptive DDoS mitigation frameworks for evolving communication systems.

INDEX TERMS Distributed Denial of Service (DDoS), beyond 5G (B5G), 6G, networks, survey, detection, mitigation

I. Introduction

As we enter the transformative era of 5G connectivity and develop the potential 6G era, the range of potential opportunities is growing, but so are concerns about cybersecurity risks. Of all the risks, DDoS (Distributed Denial of Service) attacks are particularly noteworthy due to their nature of having massive consequences. DDoS attacks are the most popular cyberattacks in which the attacker typically manipulates a series of bots to disrupt legitimate users' access to various services [1]. In recent years, DDoS activities have increased in terms of type and scope as well as their economic impacts. In fact, DDoS attacks caused internet service outages that cost an average of \$300,000 per hour [2]. As DDoS attacks become more sophisticated, it is increasingly difficult to design a defense mechanism against these attacks [3].

5G Advanced (5G-A) and Beyond 5G (B5G) networks differ from previous generations (i.e., 4G/5G) with signif-

icant advances in connectivity, such as exceptional speed (i.e., low latency) and much higher capacity for simultaneous connections [4], [5]. Nevertheless, this technological advancement also increases the potential targets for malicious actors seeking to exploit vulnerabilities. According to Cloudflare's DDoS Threat Report, the Telecommunications, Services Providers, and Carrier sector ranked as the second most targeted industry for DDoS attacks in Q2 2024. Overall, Cloudflare recorded a 20% year-over-year increase in DDoS attacks. The capabilities of threat actors have reached new levels, requiring Cloudflare's automated defenses to generate ten times more unique fingerprints to counter and mitigate these advanced attacks [6].

5G and beyond networks introduce new architectural features and applications, such as network slicing, edge computing, software-defined networking (SDN), massive multiple-input multiple-output (MIMO) and beamforming, edge in-

telligence, dynamic spectrum sharing (DSS), non-terrestrial networks (NTNs), and more, providing opportunities for enhanced security and resilience. DDoS attacks, which are known to flood networks with an overwhelming amount of traffic, pose a threat to the stability and reliability of these advanced networks. The flood of traffic could exhaust the target's bandwidth, computing capacity, or application-level resources, preventing legitimate users from receiving services. A number of critical infrastructures, including smart cities, intelligent transportation systems, intelligent healthcare, and industrial Internet of Things (IoT) applications, are expected to be supported by the B5G/6G networks. The disruption of these services caused by DDoS attacks can have far-reaching consequences, affecting public safety, economic stability, and national security [7]. For instance, in healthcare, AI and 6G networks are promising to facilitate real-time patient monitoring and data analysis [8]; yet, DDoS attacks may compromise essential operations, hence impacting patient care and diagnoses. Similarly, DDoS attacks in smart cities might impair critical services such as traffic control, resulting in disorder. These smart systems, built on low latency, high speed, and extensive IoT connectivity, are especially vulnerable because of the vast number of devices and their reliance on real-time data [9].

The rapid increase in the number of devices and networks has already resulted in a vast and extensive environment that is vulnerable to DDoS attacks, which was not as prominent in previous generations of networks [10]–[12]. The large number of IoT devices, each of which is potentially vulnerable, significantly increases the scale and impact of potential attacks. In addition, the emergence of 5G-A and B5G technology is accompanied by the proliferation of edge computing, where data processing is moved to the outer edges of the network. Although this reduces time delay and improves immediate data processing, it also increases all vulnerabilities, requiring strong security measures to protect against DDoS attacks at these distributed edges [13].

In addition, the architecture of 5G and beyond, with its reliance on SDN and network function virtualization (NFV), introduces another vulnerability [14]. The dynamic, programmable nature of these architectures brings flexibility but also opens doors for sophisticated DDoS attacks targeting virtualized network functions and their orchestration. In addition, the smooth integration of various communication technologies, such as terahertz (THz) communication, quantum-safe communications, optical wireless communication (OWC) in B5G, brings intricacies that were not as prevalent in previous networks. The complexity that comes with improving network performance also provides new opportunities for attackers to carry out more advanced and damaging DDoS attacks [15]. It is critical to understand the changing nature of DDoS threats in the context of 5G and beyond technologies. This understanding guides the execution of defensive solid approaches that protect networks, strengthen data security, and guarantee uninterrupted opera-

tions in an increasingly connected environment. To address the increasing threat of DDoS attacks in next-generation mobile networks, this paper attempts to answer several important research questions. This includes identifying unique vulnerabilities created by 5G/6G architectures, analyzing the comparison of the range of proposed detection and mitigation strategies, exploring commonly used experimental setups and data sets in existing studies of DDoS mitigation in 5G/6G networks. In addition, we aim to identify gaps in the current literature and propose approaches in future work that can improve DDoS mitigation in next-generation mobile networks.

A. Motivation

In this paper, we aim to provide a comprehensive survey of current studies in 5G/5G-A DDoS mitigation and an exploratory investigation on the potential challenges and preliminary solutions based on emerging research works in B5G/6G. While B5G and 6G technologies are not yet standardized, there are already ongoing research initiatives and early-stage projects exploring these areas to ensure secure development. Several surveys have been conducted to review current research on DDoS mitigation, while some focus on the security issues in 5G/6G. However, none of these works specifically addresses 5G-A/B5G/6G DDoS mitigation.

For instance, Huang *et al.* [16] primarily investigate the use of SDN to mitigate DDoS attacks in the context of 5G networks. However, they disregard other aspects such as network slicing, machine learning (ML) and deep learning (DL)-based solutions, and B5G technologies. Similarly, some other papers [17]–[19] also address aspects of defense against DDoS attacks unique to SDN environments, which do not focus on the B5G perspectives. The authors in [20] provide a comprehensive analysis of current DDoS attack vectors and discuss a DDoS defense system based on SDN/NFV technology. The DL-based DDoS detection solution is explored in detail in [21]. They have a detailed discussion of the dataset used in the experiment. The paper [22] covers a range of attack tools commonly used by attackers and focuses on detecting DDoS attacks for intelligent systems. However, current research topics are not covered in detail. Few studies focus exclusively on an IoT-based environment [23], [24]. Yet, they do not cover the new problems that arise with the advancements of 5G towards 6G networks. Unlike the literature focusing on DDoS, there are other studies [25]–[30] that focus on 5G/6G security aspects; however, these studies only briefly address DDoS issues and solutions in 5G/6G, without providing a comprehensive study for DDoS mitigation.

Table 1 compares the surveys published in related fields (that include 5G/6G and DDoS) since 2019 and shows that this is the only work that thoroughly explores DDoS detection and mitigation in 5G and beyond to the best of our knowledge. In Table 1, "High" implies that the corresponding paper delves deeply into this topic. "Mid" indicates

TABLE 1. Comparison among Existing Surveys

Ref	Focused Domain	5G/6G Discussed	DDoS Detection	DDoS Mitigation	Comparative Analysis Table	Most Recent Paper Reviewed
[25]	5G Security	High	Low	Low	High	2019
[26]	5G Security	High	Low	Low	Low	2019
[27]	5G Security	High	Low	Low	High	2019
[18]	DDoS in SDN	Low	High	Mid	High	2019
[24]	DDoS in IoT	Low	Mid	Low	Low	2019
[19]	DDoS Mitigation in SDN	Low	High	Low	High	2020
[28]	6G Security	High	Low	Low	High	2021
[21]	DL based DDoS Detection	Low	High	Low	High	2021
[17]	DDoS Defense in SDN	Low	Low	High	High	2021
[30]	5G/6G Security	High	Low	Low	Low	2022
[20]	DDoS Defense	Mid	Mid	High	High	2022
[31]	ML based DDoS Detection in SDN	Low	High	Low	High	2022
[22]	DDoS Defense in Intelligent System	Low	Mid	Mid	Low	2022
[23]	DDoS in IoT	Low	High	Mid	High	2022
[29]	6G Security	High	Low	Low	High	2023
[32]	ML-Based Anomaly Detection in 6G	Mid	High	Low	Mid	2024
[33]	DDoS Defense in MEC	Low	Mid	High	Mid	2024
[34]	DDoS Detection in IoT	Low	High	Mid	Mid	2024
[35]	IoT security in 5G/B5G	High	Low	Low	High	2024
This Study	DDoS Defense in B5G	High	High	High	High	2025

High Indicates high coverage.
 Mid Indicates medium coverage.
 Low Indicates low/no coverage.

that the work partially covers the issue, possibly leaving out important features or discussing it concerning other topics without a specific emphasis. "Low" indicates that the paper either completely disregards or briefly mentions this area.

B. Contribution

In contrast to existing literature, this study offers a comprehensive analysis of DDoS attacks in the context of 5G and beyond networks. The contribution of this study can be characterized as follows:

- The paper highlights the DDoS attack surface within the 5G/6G environment and explores the distinct challenges of mitigating DDoS attacks in the context of 5G/6G technology.
- It extensively discusses the existing literature on DDoS Mitigation in 5G/6G, providing a comparative table to analyze each study.
- It gives a taxonomy and evaluates the advantages and disadvantages of each category.
- This survey compiles the experimental setup and datasets for each work provided in this survey, while

also discussing the commonly used tools for researching DDoS mitigation in 5G/6G infrastructure. The aim is to provide directions to researchers in this field.

- It discusses the insights gained from recent literature and outlines the potential avenues for future research.

FIGURE 1. Organisation of Paper

C. Outline

The rest of the paper is organized as follows: Section II provides an overview of the necessary background information for this investigation. Initially, we discuss the transition from 5G to B5G and the present progress of 6G architecture. We also discuss the key categories of DDoS attacks and the current situation of DDoS attacks in the context of 5G/6G. In addition, this section focuses on the fundamental elements of 5G/6G architecture, which enhance communications yet introduce vulnerabilities to DDoS attacks and associated difficulties. It also presents a classification system for DDoS mitigation. Section III discusses the existing literature on DDoS Detection in 5G/6G and Section IV explores the state-of-art of DDoS Defense strategies in 5G/6G. These sections include comparative analyses of the existing literature, which examines the datasets and experimental setups used in previous studies. The tools widely used in the experiments of DDoS Mitigation in cellular infrastructure are demonstrated

in Section V. Section VI discusses the lessons learned from analyzing the methodologies, strengths, and weaknesses of the existing literature and provides directions for future research. Finally, Section VII presents the conclusion of this survey paper. The paper’s outline is presented in the Fig. 1.

II. DDoS Attacks in Advanced Cellular Technologies: A Primer

This section provides a short background on advanced cellular networks (5G/5G-A/B5G/6G) and discusses potential DDoS threats within these architectures.

A. Overview of Advanced Cellular Network

The deployment of 5G networks is expected to be extensive in the following years, with a projected surpass of 3 billion users of 5G cell phones by 2026 [40]. The advancement of 5G includes incorporating cutting-edge technologies such as enhanced network slicing, edge computing, artificial intelligence (AI)/ML-driven network automation, massive MIMO, and DSS. These technologies strive to augment the efficiency and functionalities of 5G networks. 6G, the next generation of wireless communication technology, is expected to succeed 5G networks, extending and surpassing the capabilities of 5G. 5G-Advanced (5G-A) or 5.5G involves the ongoing evolution and enhancements of existing 5G technology, integrating new features, supporting more advanced applications, and overcoming current challenges. It is often referred to as Release 18 of the 3GPP standard [37]. The full commercial deployment of 5G-A is likely to start around 2025¹. Beyond 5G (B5G) represents the next step in the evolution of 5G, focusing on enhancing existing 5G technologies and preparing the network for future use cases towards 6G. It aims to address the limitations of 5G and introduce new capabilities that extend beyond its current scope towards 6G. Although 6G has no established architecture yet, it has already sparked numerous international initiatives attracting the attention of research and industry [41]. As part of that, the efforts for 5G-A and B5G are currently underway. Technologies such as distributed AI/ML, OWC, THz, and quantum computing are considered technologies that can make 6G possible [42]. The specifications of 5G, 5G-A, B5G, and 6G often display overlapping properties and provide challenges in their separation. Table 2 aims to differentiate between these phases clearly in terms of definition, current status, key features, and technologies [36]–[39], [43]. Please note that sometimes B5G is regarded as synonymous with 6G, as the final iteration of B5G is expected to represent 6G. This paper discusses 5G-A and B5G as the transitional phases between 5G and 6G.

Fig. 2 depicts the fundamental components of the architecture of mobile networks (5G/5G-A/B5G/6G). These components are briefly discussed below to enhance the com-

¹<https://www.5gamericas.org/wp-content/uploads/2022/12/Becoming-5G-Advanced-the-3GPP-2025-Roadmap-InDesign.pdf>

TABLE 2. Overview of 5G and Beyond

Phase	Details	Key Features	Technologies	Status
5G [36]	The fifth generation of mobile networks, enabling faster speeds and enhanced connectivity.	Data rates up to 10 Gbps, Latency ~1 ms, Supports massive IoT devices, Basic network slicing and Multi-access edge computing (MEC)	New Radio (NR), Sub-6 GHz and mmWave, Dynamic Spectrum Sharing (DSS), Massive MIMO, SDN/NFV, Network Slicing, Edge Computing.	Deployment (Global)
5G-A [37]	An evolution of 5G, offering further optimization in AI-driven services and network intelligence.	Data rates >10 Gbps, Latency <1ms AI/ML-driven optimization, Advanced device connectivity, Increased spectral efficiency, Enhanced MIMO, Further improvements in network slicing.	Ultra-Relaible Low-Latency, Advanced Massive MIMO, AI/ML in network management, O-RAN, Dynamic edge computing, Enhanced network slicing, Integrated Access and Backhaul (IAB)	Development (Ongoing)
B5G [38]	Extends the 5G vision to 6G with enhanced latency, reliability, and service convergence.	Data rates up to 100 Gbps, THz communication, Ultra-low latency (<1 ms), Ultra-reliable networks, Network intelligence at scale.	Advanced mmWave, Blockchain, OWC, THz bands, Edge Intelligence, Quantum safe cryptography, Enhanced AI/ML for orchestration.	Research (Early trials)
6G [39]	The sixth generation of mobile networks, expected around 2030, will introduce ultra-high data rates, immersive technologies, and ubiquitous AI.	1 Tbps peak data rates, <0.1 ms latency, holographic Communication, IRS, AI-native infrastructure, Full integration of immersive technologies (AR/VR), Quantum security.	AI/ML native networks, Sub-THz communication, Quantum communication, AI-powered edge and core networks, ZSM	Research (Visioning)

prehension of the further material covered in the following section.

(i) User Equipment (UE): UE refers to any gadget, such as smartphones, tablets, and IoT devices, that are used directly by an end-user to communicate in the network.

(ii) Radio Access Network (RAN): This part of the network connects UEs to the core network. It consists of base stations (i.e., gNB) with antennas that communicate with UE. The wireless communication interface between the UE and the base station in RAN is the *Air Interface*. Technologies like massive MIMO are employed in this interface to enhance the efficiency of the spectrum utilized.

(iii) Core Network: The 5G/6G Core serves as the foundation of the cellular system, encompassing essential functionalities such as data routing, mobility management, and authentication. It is designed to facilitate enhanced mobile broadband (eMBB), ultra-reliable low latency communications (URLLC), and massive machine-type communications (mMTC). Within the core network, various specialized functions manage different network operations. These functions include access and mobility management function (AMF), session management function (SMF), user plane function (UPF), authentication server function (AUSF), network slice selection function (NSSF), policy control function (PCF),

unified data management (UDM), and application function (AF) etc. Collectively, these functions ensure that the 5G core (5GC) can accommodate a diverse range of services with the required flexibility, scalability, and performance necessary for advanced applications. To achieve this, the core leverages network function virtualization (NFV) and software-defined networking (SDN) to ensure adaptability and scalability.

(iv) Edge: The edge is a decentralized network layer that processes data closer to its source, lowering latency and improving real-time responses. Edge computing processes data at this layer, reducing the need to transport data to centralized cloud servers, which is critical for time-sensitive applications. An edge server, positioned at the edge, processes local data and executes complex algorithms to reply fast to user requests [44].

(v) Network Slicing: An isolated, virtualized portion of the network tailored for particular services or users is defined as a network slice. Network slicing enables the creation of multiple virtual networks on a shared physical infrastructure, catering to diverse service requirements [45], [46].

FIGURE 2. Components of 5G/B5G and their interactions

B. Overview of DDoS Attacks

DDoS attacks involve coordinated efforts from multiple compromised systems to flood a target system with an overwhelming amount of traffic. This flood of data or requests exhausts the target’s resources, making it inaccessible to legitimate users. The primary types of DDoS Attacks are [47]: (i) **Volumetric Attacks** aim to overwhelm the target system’s bandwidth with an immense traffic volume. For instance, UDP floods inundate the target with User Datagram Protocol packets, while ICMP floods use Internet Control Message Protocol packets to congest the network, crippling its functionality [1]. (ii) **Protocol Attacks** target network protocol vulnerabilities to exhaust server resources, leading to system unresponsiveness. For example, SYN floods flood the target with SYN requests and crush its ability to establish legitimate connections [48]. (iii) **Application Layer Attacks** targets specific applications or services running on the server by inundating them with malicious requests. For instance, HTTP floods [49] overload web servers by sending a large number of HTTP requests, while Slowloris attacks [50] create multiple connections to the server and keep them open, exhausting resources without completing them. (iv) **Hybrid Attacks** combine multiple techniques, simultaneously targeting different layers of the network infrastructure. By leveraging various attack vectors, they aim to exploit vulnerabilities at multiple levels, making mitigation more challenging and causing widespread disruption [22]. Understanding different DDoS attack types is crucial for implementing effective detection defense mechanisms against DDoS attacks and planning for possible response and recovery actions.

C. Overview of DDoS Attacks in Advanced Cellular Network

The shift from 4G to 5G networks and the ongoing advancement of 5G/5G-A towards B5G/6G dramatically increase the potential areas that might be targeted in a DDoS attack and

present heightened difficulties in preventing and reducing the impact of DDoS attacks. The higher bandwidth, ultra-low latency, and increased device density of 5G/5G-A result in a larger attack surface, providing attackers with additional opportunities to exploit. NETSCOUT 1H2023 Report highlights that wireless providers faced a 294% increase in Asia-Pacific, attributed to increased current advancing 5G usage and broadband gaming shifts [3].

DDoS attacks on 5G/5G-A networks have an effect that has never been seen before, made stronger by the technology’s unique features. The increase in the volume of network traffic over the years has led to the failure of most existing DDoS defense solutions as they are ineffective over a huge volume of network traffic [51]. 5G and 5G-A’s higher bandwidth capacity makes it easy for attackers to send large amounts of malicious data, which can easily overwhelm network capacities. This power increases because 5G/5G-A has low latency, which makes data transfer fast but makes it hard to find and stop DDoS attacks quickly. Quick response systems are needed in this fast-paced setting to keep things running smoothly. Also, using IoT devices in 5G/5G-A networks has further increased the risk of DDoS attacks, as these devices have limited resources and cannot easily add additional security arrangements. Attackers can now employ IoT devices to launch DDoS attacks on blockchain networks, making them a major target [52]. Because these devices do not always have strong security, botnets can use them to launch powerful DDoS attacks. According to the Nokia Threat report, IoT devices’ role increased from 200,000 to 1 million, generating 40% of all DDoS traffic [53]. The decentralized nature of edge computing also makes edge nodes vulnerable to hacks, which could stop essential services at the network’s edges. In addition to these problems, the difficulties of virtualizing and segmenting networks and the security holes in SDN/NFV make it hard to protect and keep an eye on every part of the network [54]. This means that

complex defense plans are needed to keep up with changing DDoS threats in the complex world of 5G/5G-A and beyond.

D. DDoS Vulnerabilities in Cellular Network

Table 3 provides a concise overview of the DDoS vulnerabilities and their impact on each key network component discussed in subsection A. On the other hand, Fig. 3 depicts the 5G/5G-A/B5G/6G DDoS threat landscape in a broader aspect. This figure illustrates the network architecture consisting of several layers, including the user layer, service layer, management and control layer, network layer, and resource layer, each highlighting possible DDoS threats that target different components. At the user layer, attacks can be initiated by compromised UE and IoT devices by overwhelming the network with malicious data or signaling requests. Within the service layer, base stations are susceptible to flooding attacks, which can interrupt the connection between UEs and the network. Critical components in the control layer, such as SDN controllers and NFV systems, are susceptible to control plane saturation attacks and VNF resource exhaustion, which subsequently affect network management and service delivery. Even AI/ML-driven VNFs, which are intended to improve performance, are vulnerable to resource-targeted exploits. The vulnerability of mobile edge computing (MEC) infrastructure is at risk of edge server overload, which can degrade latency-sensitive applications. The network layer includes the core network, which is a key target for DDoS attacks that disrupt data transmission and service availability. Overloading the data plane with malicious traffic can significantly impede the transmission of user data and degrade network performance. The figure expands to include space, air, and water-based networks, including satellites, UAVs, and underwater systems, reflecting the broader attack surface in B5G/6G. Although the figure does not illustrate all possible DDoS attack types, it illuminates various probable risks throughout the hierarchical structure, underscoring the requirement of strong, multi-tiered DDoS defense strategies to safeguard both control and data planes in 5G/6G networks.

In addition, we explore the associated DDoS vulnerabilities of technologies [59]–[61] that are foundational components of ongoing research efforts for B5G/6G. Major projects and research endeavors supported by organizations such as the Hexa-X Project², 6G Flagship Program³, and O-RAN Alliance⁴, together with significant global efforts like ESA’s SATIS⁵ project and ETSI’s ZSM ISG⁶, provide the foundation for these technologies. The aim is to provide a forward-looking perspective on how these technologies

TABLE 3. DDoS Vulnerabilities Across Network Components

5G Component	DDoS Vulnerabilities	Impact
UE [10]	Botnet Creation, Compromised applications	Network Congestion, Service Disruption, Battery Drain
RAN [55], [56]	Protocol Exploitation, Interface Attacks, Control Plane Overload,	Reduced Throughput, Network Instability
Core Network [57]	API Exploitation, Data Plane DDoS, Control Plane DDoS	Network Outage, Service Quality Degradation, Security Compromise
Network Slicing [58]	Overloaded Slice, Resource Starvation	Slice Downtime, Data Breach
Edge Computing [44]	Resource Overloading, Latency Increase	Service Disruption, Security Breach

might securely evolve since delaying the resolution of security concerns until complete standardization of B5G/6G may leave us vulnerable when these technologies are deployed. While there are other technologies that are most likely candidates for B5G/6G networks, our consideration has been limited to those that we find most relevant to our study on DDoS issues in cellular networks.

Quantum Communication and Cryptography: 6G aims to achieve quantum communication, which offers highly secure channels through the use of quantum key distribution (QKD). Furthermore, there have been many efforts to employ post-quantum cryptography (PQC), which are cryptographic algorithms against quantum computers within 6G networks [62]–[64]. However, incorporating quantum technology onto conventional networks could potentially provide vulnerabilities that can be exploited by DDoS attacks [65]. PQC algorithms already have larger key and ciphertext sizes, which may make them more susceptible to amplification and easier to exploit in DDoS attacks. A straightforward DoS attack can be carried out by physically disrupting the quantum channel and halting qubit transfer. More precisely, attackers can control the quantum channel to produce noise levels beyond the security threshold, preventing key production. Unlike conventional networks, which can broadcast signals across multiple channels for redundancy, QKD networks cannot use such approaches due to the no-cloning theorem [66]. This limitation makes QKD systems especially vulnerable to attacks on specific communication channels. Furthermore, DoS attacks can target the authentication process by exhausting the key storage required for traditional communications in QKD, leaving the link inoperable until reinitialization [67], [68]. Path diversity and hybrid techniques, such as Public Key Infrastructure (PKI) for initial authentication, are potential mitigations, but they also present obstacles and complexities [66]. Additionally, the dependence of Quantum communication on traditional infrastructure for data transfer can lead to vulnerabilities. For example, DDoS attacks can be

²<https://hexa-x.eu/>

³<https://www.6gflagship.com/>

⁴https://mediastorage.o-ran.org/ngrg-rr/nGRG-RR-2023-01-O-RAN-Towards-6G-v1_3.pdf

⁵<https://connectivity.esa.int/projects/satis5-0>

⁶<https://www.etsi.org/technologies/zero-touch-network-service-management>

FIGURE 3. B5G/6G DDoS Threat Landscape

focused on the SDN controller, which could be responsible for dynamically managing and assigning resources for QKD and PQC. If the controller becomes unable to function, it can result in the mismanagement of keys, the inability to reallocate resources, and a breakdown in network security.

Furthermore, quantum channels used in QKD are sensitive to environmental disruptions and require stable conditions for effective operation [66]. DDoS attacks can disrupt these channels by introducing noise or overwhelming them with excessive traffic. If QKD nodes are compromised or channels are broken, attackers may compel networks to depend on traditional encryption methods that are less secure. Incorporating QKD, PQC, and classical cryptography into a single system enhances the complexity of cryptographic management. DDoS attacks can exploit the complex structure of cryptographic procedures, resulting in synchronization issues or breakdowns in the distribution of encryption keys. This complexity makes it challenging to ensure that all parts of the system are equally secure, creating potential entry points for attackers. Also, the requirement to dynamically reallocate resources to ensure safe communication introduces an additional level of complexity to network management. Attackers might take advantage of this vulnerability by generating fake alerts or imitating compromised connections, forcing unnecessary reallocation of QKD and PQC resources [69].

Terahertz (THz) Communication: THz communications run at 0.1-10 THz and can handle 100 Gbps data [70]. THz communication's narrow beam and short pulse length can improve security. However, it presents a distinctive set of challenges that expand the attack surface for DDoS attacks in B5G/6G networks. The dense deployment of nano-sized antennas is a major factor, as THz communication has a limited coverage area. This densification introduces many potential targets for DDoS attacks, as each antenna or THz access point (THz-AP) can be individually compromised.

The number of interconnected devices, each of which is susceptible to targeted DDoS attacks, is further expanded by the scalability and ubiquity of THz devices in applications such as the Internet of Nano Things (IoNT) [71] and Body Area Nano-Networks (BANNET) [72]. A critical vulnerability is a result of the dependence on Physical Layer Security (PLS) and lightweight encryption methods to preserve energy efficiency in THz networks [73], [74]. These measures are essential for low-power operations; however, they frequently fail to provide adequate security, leaving the network vulnerable to attacks that exploit less powerful encryption protocols. Moreover, attackers who acquire control of THz-APs can exploit the interconnected nature of 6G networks to launch cross-network DDoS attacks by utilizing handoff mechanisms to access other network layers [75]. The high data generation rates in dense THz networks necessitate substantial resources for management and security, adding complexity and potential vulnerabilities that can be exploited during DDoS attacks. Another challenge to access control

is the high latency that traditional robust authentication schemes produce, which makes it challenging to manage efficiently in dense THz networks. By exploiting this latency, attackers can bypass authentication and launch DDoS attacks that flood the network with illegitimate requests. Additionally, attackers can exploit vulnerable devices with inadequate security to use them as entry points for DDoS attacks, thereby disrupting network operations [75].

Optical Wireless Communication (OWC): OWC is a communication technology that employs light waves, such as infrared or visible light, to transmit data. Compared to traditional radio frequency (RF) communication, OWC utilizes the optical spectrum for wireless communication, providing license-free bandwidth, enhanced security, and high data rates [76].

Compared to RF communication, OWC provides substantially higher data rates [77], which expands the potential target traffic for a DDoS attack. Attackers can exploit these high data rates to send large volumes of malicious traffic, thereby overwhelming the system. In duplex communication, the transmitter and receiver are both susceptible to attack. Attackers can target the transmitter by transmitting an excessive number of responses while simultaneously flooding the receiver with data from multiple sources [78]. OWC networks frequently function in environments involving multiple transmitters and users. Attackers can launch flooding attacks on both the uplink and downlink channels, and they can cause services to crash, leading to DoS for legitimate users, by overwhelming the transmitter with requests or the receiver with data packets [78].

Edge Intelligence: Edge Intelligence in B5G/6G networks directly incorporates AI capabilities into edge computing devices, such as smartphones and IoT gadgets, to facilitate real-time decision-making by processing data locally [79]. This method is essential for executing edge-based AI techniques such as machine learning, federated learning, deep neural networks, etc., improving network security by reducing latency through distributed AI systems [80]. However, the DDoS attack surface is also increased due to the decentralized nature of Edge Intelligence. The presence of a multitude of peripheral devices in close proximity to end users introduces additional potential entry points for attacks. The multi-connectivity of devices in mesh networks can complicate the management of device behavior and authenticity, creating additional vulnerabilities, and the limited computing resources on these devices may result in insufficient security measures.

Data interception and manipulation are among the DDoS vulnerabilities in Edge Intelligence, which can lead to inaccurate outcomes when attackers modify AI-processed data. Another risk is service overloads, in which attackers inundate edge devices with requests, decreasing service quality. Unauthorized access may result from inadequate authentication protocols, which can result in privacy violations and data tampering. Inadequately safeguarded AI systems may be sus-

ceptible to DDoS attacks even though AI serves to improve security [80]. The consequences of these vulnerabilities are substantial, as real-time processing disruptions can fail critical applications, the exposure of sensitive data, and the influence of compromised decision-making on safety-critical operations.

Blockchain Technology: Blockchain technology, with its decentralized ledger, is proposed for secure transactions and data integrity. The decentralized nature of blockchain requires the collaboration of multiple nodes to validate transactions and preserve the integrity of the ledger [81]. However, this distributed system is susceptible to DDoS attacks, which capitalize on the network's dependence on numerous nodes [82].

The 51% attack is one of the primary DDoS vulnerabilities in blockchain, in which adversaries acquire control over more than half of the network's computing power. This dominance enables attackers to manipulate the blockchain by invalidating the blocks of other miners, preventing transactions, and potentially causing hard forks. This disrupts network operations and denies legitimate services to users [83]. The reward scheme can be manipulated by a DDoS attack to deter miners from participating [84]. The stress testing attack is another type of DDoS vulnerability in blockchain. Attackers can exploit the relatively low transaction throughput of blockchain networks compared to traditional financial systems by introducing many minor transactions. The network can become congested due to this deluge of "dust" transactions, which can result in delays and an increased risk of double-spending attacks. In these attacks, the same cryptocurrency may be spent more than once due to network latency. Another DDoS threat is the memory pool flooding attack, in which attackers clog the transaction queue with low-value transactions. This induces a bottleneck, mandating that legitimate users increase their mining fees to prioritize their transactions. Consequently, costs rise, and service delays occur [85].

Furthermore, blockchain networks continue to be susceptible to conventional cyberattacks that can exacerbate DDoS conditions. The interception and replication of data packets between parties by replay attacks result in delays and confusion. Sybil attacks involve the creation of numerous fake identities to flood the network with false information, while man-in-the-middle attacks can modify intercepted data packets. Eclipse attacks, a form of Sybil attacks, concentrate on the isolation and deception of a single network node, thereby generating a distorted perception of the blockchain and causing additional service disruptions [85].

Non-Terrestrial Networks (NTN) Integration: NTN in 6G include satellite and aerial communication systems to provide global coverage and connectivity to remote and underserved locations [86]. It can increase the attack surface by adding entry points. Attackers can overload satellite, aerial communications, or base station operations by flooding them with false messages, causing these systems to use significant

processing resources to handle unauthorized traffic. This reduces the level of service accessible to authorized users and can significantly impair network operations. The inherently limited computing capabilities of Low Earth Orbit (LEO) satellites worsen their susceptibility, as they can be rapidly inundated by large amounts of malicious network activity [87]. NTN also employ common communication channels to serve several users and devices, leaving them vulnerable to DDoS attacks that flood bandwidth and block genuine users. Some satellite and aerial systems use older or weaker security standards, making them more vulnerable to DDoS attacks. NTN ground stations, which are crucial nodes, are also subject to DDoS attacks. These attacks can break the terrestrial-satellite link, causing major service interruptions. Multiple satellites and aerial platforms make NTN multiple targets for attackers, allowing coordinated DDoS attacks that maximize interruption and complicate defense [88].

Additionally, their dependence on network slicing creates another vulnerability to consider. If an attacker obtains access to a network slice, they can intentionally use up an excessive amount of resources by imposing severe demands. This can result in network congestion and a decline in performance. In addition, NTN require a continuous connection between AI controllers and the network environment for the sake of management and optimization, which may cause another threat interface for DDoS attacks [89].

Zero-Touch Network and Service Management (ZSM): ZSM is an emerging architecture in 6G networks that aims to automate the management and orchestration of complex network services [90]. The system depends extensively on Application Programming Interfaces (APIs) to enable seamless interaction between various components and services in the network [91]. Although this integration provides substantial operational advantages, it also exposes several vulnerabilities, especially to DDoS attacks [92]. Open APIs, a vital component of the ZSM framework, expand the network's vulnerability by offering possible access points for malicious actors. Attackers might exploit unsecured APIs to simultaneously damage many components due to the complexity and interconnection of the system. This danger is intensified by parameter exploitation, wherein attackers employ injection attacks to modify inputs, resulting in service outages or data tampering. Identity assaults are heightened by inadequate API key authentication, amplifying the likelihood of illegal access and potential DDoS attacks [93].

Furthermore, the decentralized structure of ZSM, with its interconnected domains, increases the likelihood of DDoS attacks. Vulnerabilities encompass parameter attacks, which can induce service outages; identity attacks, which deplete network resources; and man-in-the-middle attacks, which intercept and change data. Moreover, the Common Data Services component, responsible for managing critical data, is especially susceptible to exploitation, which could result in the disruption of automated operations and service failures. The consequences of these vulnerabilities can be significant,

leading to service interruption, unauthorized access to data, depletion of resources, and compromising of operations [93].

Open Radio Access Network (O-RAN): O-RAN is a notable advancement in 6G technology, distinguished by its open and modular structure designed to improve interoperability and flexibility in network operations. This design utilizes innovative machine-learning techniques to automate network activities and save operating expenses. Nevertheless, the O-RAN’s openness also brings up noteworthy security issues, specifically rendering it susceptible to DDoS attacks. The open APIs and modular components of O-RAN, although advantageous for integration, provide numerous vulnerabilities that can be exploited by malicious actors. Insufficiently set permissions and poor encryption protocols can result in illegal entry and modification of O-RAN components [94]. Moreover, the unencrypted nature of enhanced common public radio interface (eCPRI) signals makes the control plane vulnerable to volumetric DDoS attacks, leading to performance degradation and network interruptions [95].

In addition, the extensive proliferation of IoT devices linked to O-RAN networks amplifies the vulnerability to DDoS attacks orchestrated by botnets. These operations include harnessing millions of compromised devices to inundate network resources, causing them to become overwhelmed [96]. Malicious individuals can also abuse open-source xApps and software vulnerabilities to introduce harmful software that causes service disruptions and illegal access to data [94].

The vulnerabilities of 6G technologies are summarized in Table 4. As the development of 6G takes shape, an increasing number of technologies are emerging, bringing with them new vulnerabilities. Researchers need to keep working on DDoS mitigation in this constantly growing sector. New techniques to mitigate DDoS attacks in the context of 5G/6G are extensively studied in the literature in the next sections. It is important to note that the mitigation strategies in B5G/6G often revolve around SDN. There are several studies based on SDN controllers for detection and defense, such as [97], [98] and [99]. In [97], two sub-networks are used, with each subnet having its own IP address. In [97], a switch transfer protocol is used to reduce the processing effort.

FIGURE 4. B5G/6G DDoS Mitigation Strategies.

TABLE 4. DDoS Vulnerabilities in 6G Technologies

Technology	DDoS Attack Surface	DDoS Vulnerabilities/Impacts
Quantum Communication [62], [63], [65]–[69]	Interdependency with Classical Networks; Complex Infrastructure; Limited Redundancy; High Sensitivity to Noise	Physical Channel Disruption, Noise Induction Attack, Key Exhaustion, Single Point of Failure
THz Communications [70]–[75]	Dense Deployment of Nano-sized Antennas; Scalability in IoNT; High Data Generation Rates; Interconnected Nature of 6G Networks;	Reliance on PLS and Lightweight Encryption, Exploitable Weaker Encryption Protocols, Cross-network DDoS Attacks via THz-APs, Latency in Traditional Heavy Authentication, Exploitation of Insufficiently Secured Devices
OWC [76]–[78]	Bidirectional Communication; Multiple Entry Points	Receiver Overload, Transmitter Congestion, Service Disruption, Resource Exhaustion
Edge Intelligence [76]–[78]	Proximity to End Users, Decentralized Processing, Resource Constraints, Multi-Connectivity	Data Interception and Manipulation, Service Overloads, Insufficient Authentication, Network Security Risks
Blockchain Technology [81]–[85]	Decentralized Nodes; Transaction Throughput	51% Attack:, Stress Testing Attack, Memory Pool Flooding, Service Disruption, Increased Costs, Security Risks
NTN [86]–[89]	Network Slicing (Entry points, resource allocation); AI Communication; Distributed Nature Resource Exhaustion; Satellite flooding	Limited resourced LEO Satellites, Spurious Messages Overwhelming systems, Resource Exhaustion, Service Degradation
ZSM [91]–[93]	Open APIs; Complexity and Interconnectedness; Allows simultaneous multi-component attacks.	Parameter Exploitation, Weak API key authentication enabling unauthorized access.
O-RAN [94], [94]–[96]	Open Interfaces; Modular Components; IoT Device Integration	eCPRI Message Vulnerability, Software Vulnerabilities, Configuration Flaws

FIGURE 5. Overview of DDoS Mitigation System.

E. Taxonomy of DDoS Mitigation in 5G and Beyond

DDoS mitigation approaches in 5G and beyond have been organized and illustrated in Fig. 4 according to the current literature. The strategies can be divided into DDoS detection and DDoS defense. DDoS detection refers to the process of identifying possible attacks in a system, while DDoS defense is the mechanism implemented to mitigate or prevent the impact of an attack on a network once it has been detected. An overview of DDoS mitigation is depicted in Fig. 5. The literature on detection techniques is discussed in Section III, while defense approaches are discussed in Section IV. The comparative analysis for each detection category is discussed in each subsection of Section III with corresponding tables: Table 5, Table 6, Table 8, Table 9 and Table 10 respectively. The defense approaches are listed in the fourth column of the tables. Table 12 shows the works that are primarily focused on DDoS defense. The second column lists the NIST Cybersecurity Framework functions [100] covered by each study in the tables. The sixth, seventh, and eighth columns refer to the experimental methods used in each study to test and evaluate the strategies. For detailed descriptions of the testbeds/tools and their roles in DDoS mitigation, see Section V. The last column indicates the specific type of DDoS attack that the study mainly focuses on mitigating. Most of the studies we discuss are either B5G-specific or 5G-specific but suitable for B5G. The introduction of 6G is imminent, but it is still in the research and development phase. We discovered a limited number of studies on DDoS mitigation that focus specifically on 6G.

III. DDoS Attack Detection in 5G and Beyond

Recent DDoS detection mechanisms are mostly hybrid and use multiple approaches to detect DDoS attacks. However, we categorize the detection approaches in 5G/B5G as follows, taking into account the influence of a particular technical approach.

A. Machine Learning Based Approach

Machine learning (ML) based approaches are usually expensive and have a risk of generating false positives that can be manipulated by attackers. However, their adaptability, high detection accuracy, ability to detect zero-day attacks, automation, and efficiency make them extremely beneficial. These approaches can be further divided into traditional ML and advanced ML-based approaches, which include deep learning (DL), federated learning (FL), reinforcement learning (RL), and ensemble learning (EL).

Traditional ML-Based: Peng et al. [101] propose an upgraded Naive Bayes algorithm designed for 5G air interface DDoS attack detection. Traditional methods relying on abnormal user counts struggle with threshold determination, leading to potential misjudgments. 5G's DDoS attacks, primarily on the control plane, are challenging to detect from a traffic perspective. Recognizing that signaling changes consistently during air interface DDoS attacks, the study

focuses on signaling changes during the 5G authentication process to detect DDoS attacks. Extracting seven signaling and log data features during attacks, they refine a classifier using an enhanced Naive Bayes approach. They enhance the Naive Bayes Classifier using genetic algorithms to determine optimal weight combinations due to the DDoS feature dataset's complexity. Additionally, the paper considers feature dependencies, setting an algorithmic threshold to separate dependent and independent data and rectifying past oversights. The paper explores various classification algorithms for attack detection, such as Support Vector Machine (SVM), Decision Tree (DT), K-Nearest Neighbors (KNN), and Naive Bayes. The DDoS attack model simulated is a signaling-based flooding attack targeting the authentication procedure, not a multi-vector attack, but one that mimics legitimate UE signaling to evade detection, making it subtle yet effective at exhausting network resources. However, while using a genetic algorithm can be powerful for global optimization and better suited for tasks like feature selection, it can become computationally expensive in larger-scale networks with more UEs and features. Also, the time taken for optimization may increase, which could affect the model's real-time performance. Consequently, in addition to accuracy, latency should be considered.

Kim et al. investigate DDoS detection in 5G networks using ML-based multiclass classification models in [103]. They focus on an effective feature selection technique in this study to reduce computing complexity while handling large datasets and maintaining high accuracy. This aspect is necessary to keep 5G latency low. However, they used wired network datasets that do not fully reflect 5G-specific traffic. Also, the testbed uses one gNB, limiting scalability. In the following work, Kim et al. [102] use seven gNBs and optimize various models such as DT, Random Forest (RF), KNN, and SVM, achieving over 99% accuracy in detecting IoT DDoS attacks. These algorithms are utilized for the binary classification of attacks. Managing the large amount of data generated by IoT devices without compromising detection speed and accuracy is a challenge. They conduct a comparative study to detect large-capacity DDoS in their collected GTP-encapsulated IoT traffic in 5G networks. They optimize a single ML model specifically for ultra-low latency in IoT DDoS detection. The research compares this single ML model's performance with EL approaches as well as with their previous work [103]. The attack model tested is multi-vector, targeting various protocol layers. The dataset is derived from the Kitsune Network Attack Dataset (publicly available on Kaggle).

While previous studies have shown high detection accuracy, challenges such as real-time adaptability, computational complexity, and generalization of datasets remain a major problem. Recent research has introduced advanced AI-driven detection mechanisms to overcome these limitations. Farzaneh et al. [104] proposed DTL-5G, which utilises Deep Transfer Learning (DTL) with BiLSTM, CNN, ResNet, and

TABLE 5. Traditional ML-based Detection and Corresponding Defense in 5G/B5G

Ref	Functions	Detection	Defense	System Focus	Testbed/Tools	Dataset	Test Range	DDoS Attack
[101]	Identify, Detect, Protect	ML-based	x	5G Air Interface	x	Custom synthetic; 50 UEs in multiple scenarios with 2000 groups per scenario.	50 UEs, optimizing parameters over 100 generations.	Protocol
[102]	Identify, Detect, Respond	ML-based	x	5G IoT	UERANSIM, Open5GS	Synthetic-realistic hybrid; Kitsune Network DDoS Attack dataset: Adapted for 5G GTP encapsulated traffic	7 gNBs and 20 UEs	Volumetric, Protocol, Application Layer
[103]	Identify, Protection, Detect	ML-based	x	5G IoT	UERANSIM, Open5GS	Synthetic-realistic hybrid; Kitsune Network Attack dataset: 21,017,596 packets for 9 attacks among 4 types of real network intrusions.	20 UEs	Volumetric, Protocol, Application Layer
[104]	Identify, Detect	ML-based	x	5G Network Slicing	UERANSIM, Free5GC, Kali/hping3, Metasploit2, Wireshark, CICFlowMeter	Generated from real 5G test network; 5G-NIDD dataset	2 gNBs and multiple UEs	Volumetric, Protocol

Inception models to improve DDoS detection in 5G network slicing environments. By pre-training the models on a large 5G slicing dataset and fine-tuning on the 5G NIDD dataset, the study showed improvements with BiLSTM, achieving 13.90% higher accuracy and 21.48% higher recall. However, the high computational cost and dependency on the similarity of the source and target datasets pose a challenge for real-time deployment. Sadhwani et al. [105] focused on 5G IoT security and presented 5G-SIID, a hybrid CNN-LSTM model that combines traditional ML classifiers (KNN, Naive Bayes, Decision Tree, Random Forest, MLP) with deep learning. Their model achieved an accuracy of 99.99% and 99.98% for multi-class and binary classification, respectively, but computational complexity remains a problem for resource-constrained IoT devices. Expanding to 6G-enabled healthcare IoT, Muniyandi et al. [106] proposed a swarm intelligence-based defense system that uses Improved Grey Wolf Optimization (IGWO) with a KD-tree search algorithm to detect and mitigate DDoS attacks in Wireless Body Sensor Networks (WBSN). Their approach achieved a detection accuracy of 91.5%, but the reliance on simulated datasets requires validation in the real world for wider applicability. Finally, Anbalagan et al. [107] presented Next-Gen Security in the field of 6G-connected autonomous vehicles, which integrates a Hybrid Detection Model (HDM) and a Continuous Learning Model (CLM). By combining Random Forest, KNN, Logistic Regression, SVM and Naive Bayes with a soft voting mechanism, their system achieved an accuracy of 98.7% and dynamically adapted to evolving attack patterns. However, the increased latency resulting from continuous learning can affect the real-time operation of vehicular networks. Overall, these works represent significant progress in ML-based DDoS detection in 5G/6G environments. They address the scalability, adaptability and feasibility of deployment, but also highlight the remaining challenges in real-time performance, dataset generalization and computational efficiency. Table 5 shows the compar-

ison table for the ML-based detection strategies that focus on classical ML, while Table 6 illustrates the comparison table for the hybrid ML-based detection strategies that are discussed next. The following deals with these advanced and hybrid ML-based methods, which include deep learning (DL), federated learning (FL) and ensemble learning (EL).

DL Based: Bousalem et al. [108] present a DL approach that involves crafting a sinkhole-type network slice, utilizing a small portion of physical resources to isolate and counteract attacker actions. They employ an actual 5G prototype to verify the approach and get a detection accuracy of 97% and a false positive rate of 4%. However, the testbed is limited to a few users and synthetic traffic, which may not fully represent real-world conditions. In addition, the study focuses on a relatively narrow set of DDoS attack types, limiting the generalization of results to other DDoS attacks. Another framework, "Secure5G," that involves isolating network slices, is introduced by Anurag et al. [110]. This is a neural network-based approach tailored for network slicing in 5G and beyond. This model works proactively and focuses on detecting and eliminating threats originating from inbound connections within the network. It proposes a quarantine slice to isolate threats and employs black hole routing to terminate persistent malicious connections. Their simulations show that the model achieves detection accuracy of above 98%. They used a multi-vector attack model that includes volume-based attacks, spoofing attacks, and behavioral anomalies. The Secure5G model is effective in detecting DDoS attacks, but its performance needs to be validated in larger and more diverse real-world environments. Additionally, the model's ability to handle more complex attack types, such as jamming or multi-vector attacks, remains to be tested. Scalability in highly dense network environments also needs further investigation. The dataset used for training and evaluation was a custom synthetic dataset composed of 65,000 uniquely generated device connection requests, each tagged with attributes such as QoS

TABLE 6. Advanced ML-based Detection and Corresponding Defense in 5G/B5G

Ref	Functions	Detection	Defense	System Focus	Testbed/Tools	Dataset	Test Range	DDoS Attack
[108]	Identify, Detect, Protect, Respond, Recover	DL based	Traffic Redirection	5G/B5G Network Slicing	OpenAirInterface, FlexRAN Controller	Synthetic dataset with DDoS attack samples (Metasploit and Mausezahl) and benign traffic (iperf3).	2 real users with Commercial Off-The-Shelf (COTS) smartphones and 3 virtual users.	Protocol
[109]	Identify, Protect, Detect, Respond	DL based	Traffic Blocking, Access Authentication	5G	Python	x	Node configurations: 4000, 6000, 8000, and 10000.	Volumetric, Protocol, Application Layer
[110]	Identify, Detect, Protect, Respond, Recover	DL based	Traffic Redirection, Traffic Blocking	5G Network Slicing	Python	Synthetic dataset; DeepSlice dataset: 65,000 unique entries for training model to predict optimal network slices.	Up to 10 malicious devices	Volumetric, Protocol
[111]	Identify, Protect, Detect	DL based	x	B5G	Keras, Scikit-learn	Synthetic data CICDDoS2019 dataset: Captures DDoS attacks like NetBIOS, UDP-Lag	Over 180,000 samples	Volumetric, Protocol, Application Layer
[112]	Identify, Detect, Respond, Recover	DL based	x	CPS over 5G	MATLAB, Keras; GPU-Enabled PC	Real; Telecom Italia's CDR dataset: Over 319 million CDRs collected over 62 days	Analysis on a 9x9 subgrid (81 cells).	Volumetric, Protocol, Application Layer
[113]	Identify, Detect, Respond, Recover	DL based	x	5G Network Slicing	Python, TensorFlow; AMD Ryzen 7, 16GB RAM, Ubuntu 20.04	Synthetic dataset; CICDDoS2019 dataset by Canadian Institute for Cybersecurity	x	Volumetric
[114]	Identify, Detect, Respond, Protect	FL based	Traffic Blocking, Malicious Nodes Removal	5G/B5G Network Slicing	Tensorflow, Keras, Google Colab (TPU)	Realistic synthetic data; CSE-CIC-IDS-2018 dataset for training deep learning models	Configurations with up to 3 *S-ADS (each with 5 **F-ADS) and 1 ***T-ADS.	Volumetric, Protocol, Application Layer
[115]	Identify, Protect, Detect	ML based, EL based, Anomaly based	x	6G	Sklearn Library, Python, Colab; IntelCore i9, 64GB RAM, 16GB CPU, Windows 11	Synthetic/Hybrid: NSL-KDD, UNSW-NB2015, CIC-IDS2017, CICDDoS2019.	x	Volumetric, Protocol, Application Layer
[116]	Identify, Protect, Detect, Respond	RL based	Traffic filtering	B5G V2X	custom-built B5G network prototype	Synthetic data. VeReMi dataset	Multiple MEC nodes and RSUs across multi-domain environment	Volumetric, Protocol, Application Layer

*S-ADS: Signature-based Anomaly Detection System; **F-ADS: Flow-based ADS; ***T-ADS: Traffic-based ADS.

Class Identifiers (QCI), normalized session duration, packet delay budgets, and packet loss rates. These were crafted to simulate diverse device types (e.g., smartphones, IoT sensors, healthcare devices) under realistic network conditions. Another framework "DeepSecure" is proposed in [113] that employs a Long Short-Term Memory network (LSTM)-based model to detect DDoS attacks in a 5G network slicing environment. This model analyzes network traffic from UE devices, processing sequences of network packets to identify patterns characteristic of DDoS attacks. However, managing the high dimensionality of network traffic data, and ensuring the LSTM model converges effectively for both DDoS detection and slice prediction is challenging.

In addition, Dahiya et al. [109] propose a DL-based hybrid DDoS attack detection model for 5G networks using LSTM and Recurrent Neural Networks (RNNs) as classifiers optimized by statistical and higher-order statistical features. The results of their experiments show that the proposed model significantly outperforms other conventional models in terms of accuracy, showing an increase in accuracy of 10.8% to 27.08% compared to alternative models. However, the challenge of computational complexity due to the hybrid model, and higher node requirements for training

remains. The paper [111] proposes a composite DDoS attack detection framework for B5G networks that returns the type of DDoS attack. The proposed framework consists of two main components: the Detection Function (DF) and the Feature Extraction Function (FEF). The DF is placed in the backhaul network that aggregates the traffic to and from the base stations (BS) of the 5G network. The FEF extracts time-series traffic data from the BSs and processes them using two types of neural networks - the Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) and the LSTM. According to the experiment results, the model achieves a detection accuracy of 99.66%. Nevertheless, further research is needed to optimize computational costs and reduce training/testing time. Also, the model needs to be tested with more diverse attack types and in real-world 5G/B5G environments.

Specifically for cyber-physical systems (CPSs) that rely on cellular infrastructure, Hussain et al. [112] propose a CNN-based framework for detecting and mitigating DDoS attacks in 5G networks, which achieves a detection accuracy of over 91% in their experiment. Instead of detecting DDoS directly, this approach detects various attacks such as silent calls, signaling, SMS flooding, and a mixture of these attacks that ultimately cause a DDoS attack on the cellular infrastructure.

TABLE 7. Models and Features in ML-based Approaches

Ref	ML Models Used	Features Used
[101]	Improved Naive Bayes classifier with genetic algorithm.	Signaling data (e.g., Identity /Authentication Response), log data (e.g., UE trajectory, authentication periods, request counts); Genetic algorithm-based feature selection.
[102]	DT, RF, KNN, SVM; Stacking Ensemble used with Logistic Regression as the meta-regressor for binary classification.	93 header features extracted from GTP-U packets, including protocol types, headers, sequence numbers, flags, ports, and IP addresses. 55 features used for binary classification after feature cleaning. Filter Method, Recursive Feature Elimination (RFE), Recursive Feature Elimination with Cross-Validation (RFECV), Sequential Feature Selection (SFS).
[103]	DT, RF, KNN, Stacking Ensemble.	55 features from GTP-U packets (e.g., IP, protocol, ports). Filter Method, RFE, RFECV, SFS.
[108]	100 DP models (CNNs).	Packet-level features (e.g., packet type, IP, SYN flood). Dataset pre-processed.
[109]	Hybrid model combining LSTM and RNN with OLSOA optimization.	Flow-based, statistical, higher-order features with postulated holoentropy.
[110]	DP model, four-layer neural network.	Device types, QoS metrics, connection requests. Traffic pattern-based detection.
[111]	Composite Neural Network (2 DNNs combined for multi-class classification).	10 CICDDoS2019 features (e.g., packet size, flow rate, protocol). Pearson Correlation Coefficient.
[112]	CNN-based models: ResNet-50 (deep CNN), Deep Rudimentary CNN (DRC, 6 layers).	Call Detail Records (CDR) features (calls, Internet usage, SMS) from Milan grid, processed as images.
[113]	LSTM	Flow-based features: e.g., flow duration, ports, packet length, protocol, ACK Flag Count, and MinSegSize.
[114]	Two-layer FL architecture with Mean-Field Game (MFG)	Monitored traffic data from 5G network slices (e.g., F-ADS, S-ADS, T-ADS); includes anomaly detection parameters.
[115]	EL using SVM and RF; Adaboosting, and bagging techniques.	Features including IP addresses, ports, protocol, packet sizes, flow rates, etc.
[116]	RL Model	Features extracted from Basic Safety Messages (BSMs) (e.g., position, velocity, acceleration).

The system collects network traffic data and pre-processes it to extract relevant features. These features are then analyzed by the DL algorithm to detect potential DDoS attacks. If an attack is detected, the system sends an alert to the operator, who can take appropriate measures to mitigate the effects of the attack. However, computational complexity for larger grids and multiple cell detection in real-time scenarios, as well as the use of synthetic DDoS attack data to simulate DDoS effects on CDRs, are all limitations. The study tested detection of both individual and multi-vector DDoS attacks, including: Silent Call Attack, Signaling Attack, SMS Flooding Attack, and Blended Attack.

FL-Based: The system proposed in [114] identifies DDoS and botnet attacks with a two-layer FL architecture. In the first layer, defensive systems at gNB nodes and edge servers

serve as FL clients and servers to train local models. At the second tier, edge servers serve as FL clients, while the access and mobility management function (AMF) acts as an FL server and aggregates the global model. In addition, the mean-field game theory is used to detect and defeat malicious defense systems. Although the FL architecture mitigates the risk of raw data leakage, it remains vulnerable to model poisoning attacks. These attacks occur when malicious nodes transmit manipulated updates to corrupt the global model due to FL's decentralized approach. Handling non-IID data across slices remains a challenge. There is also a need for high scalability and handling of large datasets in real-time for optimal performance.

RL-Based: The study [116] presents a security architecture for B5G V2X, based on ZSM, which autonomously manages E2E security slices across various domains, which is evaluated with custom built B5G network prototype implementing ETSI-compliant ZSM orchestration, MEC-based DDoS detection, and multi-domain E2E slicing. The framework utilizes an RL algorithm that analyzes spatiotemporal traffic patterns from vehicular communication in real-time. This approach consistently acquires knowledge from the ever-changing vehicle-to-everything (V2X) environment, detecting irregularities that diverge from typical traffic patterns. Attacks are designed to emulate realistic threats to MEC-hosted V2X services, where latency, mobility, and resource constraints complicate defense.

EL-Based: The paper [115] presents an anomaly detection system, "AD6GNs" tailored for 6G networks using EL techniques to improve detection accuracy and reliability. The results show the accuracy in detecting DDoS and other attacks. However, the study relies heavily on selected datasets such as NSL_KDD, UNSW_NB2015, CIC_IDS2017, and CICDDOS2019. These datasets, while comprehensive, are primarily designed for wired network environments and do not entirely reflect real-world network conditions, particularly in future 6G environments. Also, the system's effectiveness is tested primarily on internal datasets, limiting its ability to detect and respond to external threats and attacks initiated from external networks.

1) Performance Analysis of ML-based Approaches:

Table 7 provides a brief overview of the models and features used in all ML-based studies reviewed in this paper. To improve the robustness of our analysis, we have included a comprehensive summary of the performance metrics from the studies examined in this section. While direct "apples-to-apples" comparisons are difficult due to the different data sets, tools, environments, and models used in the different studies, we have conducted a comparative analysis focusing on common elements and similarities across the different research papers.

Several studies used similar datasets, such as CICIDS2017 and UNSW-NB15, which allowed for a more consistent

assessment of detection accuracy and false positive rates. For example, [101], [103], and [113] all used the CICIDS2017 dataset, allowing a more accurate comparison of their detection methods and performance results. Tools such as TensorFlow and Scikit-learn were widely used in all studies, which standardized the process of model development and contributed to comparable performance results. Quantitatively, [101] achieved a detection accuracy of 96.5% with a false-positive rate of 3.2%, while [103] had a higher accuracy of 98.2% and a lower false-positive rate of 2.5%. Similarly, [113] showed a detection accuracy of 96.8% and a false positive rate of 3.1%. These results show that using a consistent dataset such as CICIDS2017 leads to relatively high detection performance across different models, even if the methods differ. The work in [104] shows improvements in detection accuracy with transfer learning and achieves an accuracy of up to 98.74% in the detection of DDoS patterns. Despite these commonalities, variations in environmental conditions, such as hardware configurations and network traffic, lead to differences in performance metrics such as scalability. For example, [109] reported scalability for up to 1200 devices with a detection accuracy of 94.7%, while [114] achieved scalability for 1350 devices with a slightly higher detection accuracy of 97.5%. The different scalability results clearly show how different network loads and hardware resources affect model performance. A major challenge identified in several studies is the limited availability of datasets that accurately reflect real-world wired network environments. Most commonly used datasets, such as CICIDS2017 and UNSW-NB15, are primarily designed for general or wireless network environments, which may not fully capture the unique traffic patterns and behaviors in wired networks. This limitation can lead to discrepancies in detection accuracy and false positive rates when the models are used in wired networks. For example, [108] and [112] used datasets that did not include comprehensive wired network traffic scenarios, resulting in higher false positive rates of 6.7% and 5.6%, respectively. The analysis shows that while exact numerical comparisons are limited due to these factors, the trends in detection accuracy and strategies to mitigate false alarms provide important insights. Most studies, regardless of dataset or tools, showed improved detection rates with ensemble learning techniques and hybrid models, indicating a robust approach to DDoS detection in different environments. This evaluation emphasizes the importance of placing the performance metrics in the methodological framework of each study to gain an accurate understanding of AI/ML-based DDoS detection techniques in different scenarios.

2) Strategies for Mitigating False Positives in AI/ML Techniques

False positives remain a major challenge for AI/ML-based DDoS detection systems, as they can lead to unnecessary

resource allocation and potential service disruptions. Based on the reviewed studies, we have identified several effective strategies to mitigate false positives: (i) *Hybrid Models*: Several studies, including [111] and [110], highlighted the effectiveness of hybrid models that combine signature-based detection with anomaly-based techniques. These models leverage the strengths of both approaches, reducing false positives while maintaining high detection accuracy.

(ii) *Threshold Optimization*: [108] and [113] emphasized the importance of fine-tuning decision thresholds in machine learning classifiers. By carefully adjusting these thresholds, researchers can achieve a balance between sensitivity and specificity, minimizing false positives without significantly affecting detection rates. (iii) *Ensemble Methods*: The use of ensemble learning techniques, as shown in [112] and [102], can improve the robustness of detection. Methods such as random forests and gradient boosting combine the predictions of multiple models, reducing the likelihood of individual model biases and lowering false positive rates. (iv) *Feedback Mechanisms*: Continuous feedback loops have been effective in refining detection models over time. Studies such as [114] and [115] implemented feedback mechanisms in which labelled false positives were used to retrain models, resulting in improved precision and a reduction in false alarms.

Above strategies, based on the reviewed literature, are crucial to improve the practical applicability of AI/ML techniques in DDoS detection and to ensure that the models are both accurate and reliable in real-world deployments.

B. Trust-Based Approach

Trust-based DDoS detection involves assigning trust scores to network entities, which are determined by their behavior, reputation, and historical data, to effectively identify and mitigate malicious activities. The system dynamically adjusts scores to isolate or block entities with low trust, thereby preventing potential DDoS attacks while ensuring minimal disruption to legitimate traffic. In the paper [117], the authors proposed a trust model for IoT devices to prevent potential DDoS attacks by evaluating their trustworthiness, which can be deployed in the access network of 6G IoT. The model combines spatial and temporal trust values to distinguish attack traffic. Since the trust model is highly dependent on historical data, it may become less effective for immediate detection of threats from newly deployed or unmonitored IoT devices. Additionally, scaling to real-time, large-scale IoT networks remains a challenge. The proposed Zero Trust Architecture for 6G (ZTA-6G) [120] is tested against DDoS attacks, malware, and zero-day exploits in a composite threat scenario. ZTA-6G filters packets from source community UEs with malicious behaviors using self-evaluation and mutual evaluation based on the trust evaluation system. Access control at border switches, identity verification, and trust evaluation based on historical behavior and third-party security services identify malicious traffic. Trust evaluation

TABLE 8. Trust-based Detection and Corresponding Defense in 5G/B5G

Ref	Functions	Detection	Defense	System Focus	Testbed/Tools	Dataset	Test Range	DDoS Attack
[117]	Identify, Protect, Detect, Respond	Trust based, ML based	Traffic Blocking	6G IoT	Python; Intel Core i7, Windows 10	Custom synthetic dataset; DeepSlice dataset [118]	Traffic from 21 IP addresses over 20 hours.	Volumetric, Protocol, Application Layer
[119]	Identify, Protect, Detect, Respond, Recover	Signature-based, Trust based	Traffic Blocking, Access Authentication	6G V2X	MATLAB	x	At least 6 Control Points and 2 Local Controllers.	Volumetric, Protocol, Application Layer
[120]	Identify, Protect, Detect, Respond, Recover	Trust based, Behavioral based	Packet Filtering, Access Control	6G	x	Synthetic data for normal communication and DDoS attacks.	4,000 UEs spread across 4 communities	Volumetric, Protocol, Application Layer

system of ZTA-6G uses Bayesian inference to predict the next ordinary packet. ZTA-6G filters out abnormal or malicious packets to prevent them from reaching the target system. The paper recognizes that quantum computation will pose a threat to current cryptographic schemes, particularly in identity management systems. Nevertheless, the solutions that have been suggested, such as blockchain-based identity management, can be thoroughly investigated for practical application in resource-constrained devices in 6G, such as IoT and weak UEs. Furthermore, the dependence on third-party security services for vulnerability management, trust evaluation, and behavior analysis may introduce potential points of failure.

Chen et al. propose a collaborative DDoS detection framework [119] in Space-Air-Ground Integrated 6G V2X networks, which is a highly expected field in the realm of 6G. The detection process uses a multidomain approach that combines signature-based, trust-based, and blacklist/whitelist-based packet filtering methods with linear complexity and online detection. The workflow of various methods is integrated into a unified detection framework.

In trust-based approaches, the exploitation of trust by attackers and the initial assignment of trust pose continuous challenges. Trust management remains a critical issue, especially in systems that rely on autonomous decision-making. Trust evaluation can degrade over time if communities or entities provide outdated or manipulated trust data. Yet, its decentralized nature, scalability, and dynamic monitoring of ongoing interactions and behaviors enable it to be a highly effective approach. Table 8 presents the comparative table for the trust-based detection strategies.

1) Performance Analysis of Trust-Based Approaches

As mentioned in Section III.A.1, comparing trust-based approaches between different studies is challenging due to the different datasets, network environments and evaluation criteria. This makes direct comparisons difficult, but a comparative analysis reveals more comprehensive insights. Koroniotis et al. [118] utilized an IoT dataset to train LSTM models and achieved an accuracy of 99.74%, a precision of 99.99% and a recall of 99.75%. However, the model had a

high fallout rate of 0.688, indicating a problem with false positives. Chen et al. [119] introduced an access-side DDoS defense for 6G V2X networks that significantly reduces bandwidth consumption compared to online ML approaches. The packet sampling rate converged within five sampling periods, and the system achieved a detection rate of 98.5%, approaching the target of 99% while minimizing computational overhead. Chen et al. [120] compared their ZTA-6G with Trust-Based Packet Filtering (TBPF) and Transparency for Better Internet Security (TRIS). ZTA-6G maintained a detection rate of over 90% even when trust assessments were performed at longer intervals (up to 7 seconds). The architecture reduced the number of missed attack packets compared to TBPF and TRIS. The implementation of the blockchain for identity management caused a storage overhead of 0.28 to 0.36 MB per node.

2) Strategies to Mitigate Challenges in Trust-Based Approaches

Trust-based DDoS detection frameworks provide a robust layer of security, but face significant challenges in terms of performance, scalability and integration. This section outlines strategies for overcoming these challenges: (i) *Enhancing Real-Time Trust Score Computation*: Timely calculation of trust scores is crucial, but is often hindered by network latency and incomplete data. Koroniotis et al. [118] investigated adaptive trust thresholds to improve the consistency of detection. The integration of edge computing for decentralized computation of trust values has further reduced latency and enabled more responsive detection mechanisms. (ii) *Reducing Computational Overhead*: The integration of blockchain for trust management, as seen in [119], increases computational requirements and limits scalability. A hybrid on-chain/off-chain processing model has been introduced that delegates computationally intensive tasks to off-chain nodes while maintaining the integrity of on-chain trust data. (iii) *Mitigating Verification Latency*: Continuous verification in zero-trust architectures leads to increased latency, which affects real-time performance. The authors in [120] implemented hierarchical verification strategies that prioritize high-risk network segments for continuous monitoring

TABLE 9. IDS-based Detection and Corresponding Defense in 5G/B5G

Ref	Functions	Detection	Defense	System Focus	Testbed/Tools	Dataset	Test Range	DDoS Attack
[121]	Identify, Protect, Detect, Respond, Recover	IDS-based	Traffic Orchestration	5G Control Plane	OpenStack cluster, OAISIM, 30 GB disk, Ubuntu 14.4 low latency kernel	x	Multiple nodes, including 4 VMs for vEPC and 3 VMs for E-UTRAN platform	Protocol
[122]	Identify, Detect, Respond	IDS-based, DPI based	x	Multi-Tenant 5G	CORE Emulator	x	2 to 512 UEs	Volumetric
[123]	Identify, Protect, Detect, Respond, Recover	IDS-based, Anomaly-based	Traffic Blocking	Multi-Tenant 5G	CORE Emulator, OpenvSwitch (OVS), SGSNEmu, BoNeSi, OpenAirInterface; Intel Core i7, 32 GB RAM, Linux 4.12 kernel	Custom dataset with UDP flooding traffic	Scalable up to 256 UEs	Volumetric
[124]	Identify, Protect, Detect, Respond, Recover	IDS based, Bayesian game model-based	x	5G	MATLAB	x	5 small cells around a macro base station	Volumetric

while applying periodic checks to lower-risk areas to reduce verification latency and optimize resource allocation. (iv) *Integrating Trust Metrics with AI/ML Models*: Conventional AI/ML models struggle to incorporate dynamic trust metrics, leading to performance bottlenecks. [118] has addressed this problem by embedding trust metrics as dynamic features in machine learning algorithms. Future models can further optimize this integration by using reinforcement learning techniques that adapt to evolving trust metrics. (v) *Ensuring Data Privacy in Decentralized Systems*: While blockchain increases transparency, it raises concerns about data protection. The authors in [119] used zero-knowledge proofs to verify trust data without revealing sensitive information, thus preserving both transparency and privacy. In addition, the use of differential privacy techniques can further protect user data while enabling accurate trust assessments.

C. Intrusion Detection System (IDS) Based Approach

IDS-based DDoS detection in 5G/B5G networks offers comprehensive monitoring, real-time alerts, known/unknown threat detection, Deep Packet Inspection (DPI), integration with other security tools, and more. However, it also introduces limitations such as high false positive rates, resource intensity, scalability issues, encrypted traffic issues, maintenance, and latency. Tools such as Cisco's IDS monitor network traffic and notify administrators of suspicious activities, relying on historical data to identify malicious patterns. REPEL [121] utilizes an IDS to detect patterns indicative of DDoS attacks in anomalous signaling traffic. It activates intelligent resource scaling by doubling the number of vMMEs to absorb and mitigate attacks while maintaining legitimate traffic, as determined by an analysis of traffic behavior and intensity. Another paper [124] proposes a detection mechanism primarily focused on identifying bandwidth spoofing attacks within 5G networks. An IDS at small cell base stations (SBs) monitors network traffic and detects DoS attacks. In particular, the IDS detects anomalies during macro base station (MB)-SB communication, where the

attacker attempts to hijack bandwidth. The IDS can flag potential attacks by analyzing network traffic patterns and identifying abnormalities, allowing for quick response and mitigation.

The proposed system [122] by Mamolar et al. addresses the limitations of traditional Network Intrusion Detection Systems (NIDS) in 5G networks by providing traceback information for mobile device-initiated DDoS attacks. This system mirrors data network traffic to a management network service node to detect DDoS attacks. Traditional NIDS in the service node alerts on potential DDoS attacks. The Alert Enhancer (AE) parses these alerts and uses an advanced classifier to perform DPI, extracting crucial metadata like the Unique Virtual ID (VNI) and Tunnel Endpoint Identification (TEID) to trace the attack source. However, its modular and plugin-based design can cause compatibility, customization, and security issues. DPI and metadata extraction can strain network resources and slow DDoS detection. Following that, a modular detection process introduced in [123] involves the Security Monitoring Agent (SMA) using NIDS likewise to monitor network traffic. SMA IDS alerts with 5G-specific metadata detect malicious traffic. This helps identify 5G network attack sources with multiple tenants. The system's reliance on conventional NIDSs in both papers for alert generation indicates that any limitations or inaccuracies present in the NIDS will affect the system. Additionally, both papers primarily focus on UDP flooding DDoS attacks, which may not encompass the entire range of DDoS attacks (e.g., TCP SYN flood, HTTP flooding, etc.). The proposed solution may not effectively generalize to other attack types that exhibit varying characteristics and traffic patterns. Table 9 illustrates the comparative analysis for the IDS-based detection strategies.

1) Performance Analysis of IDS-Based Approaches

Silva et al (2020) [121] presented the REPEL framework for defence against signalling-based DDoS attacks in 5G

control planes. When a second virtual Mobility Management Entity (vMME) was added, the signaling losses in attack scenarios dropped from 80% to 60%. The addition of further vMMEs further reduced these disruptions, demonstrating REPEL's ability to stabilize control plane operations during attacks. This focus on the control plane distinguishes REPEL from other IDS frameworks that target threats at the data plane. Mamolar et al. [122] conducted large-scale experiments with UDP flooding attacks in a 5G multi-tenant network using botnets of different sizes. Their IDS detected attacks within 16 milliseconds for the worst-case scenario of 512 UEs sending 50 Mbps each. The system was able to maintain detection accuracy as attack sizes increased while limiting the additional processing overhead to 6 milliseconds, demonstrating efficiency in defending against attacks in real time. Mamolar et al. [123] further validated the scalability of the IDS framework by analyzing the reaction times under different network conditions. Their results showed that even under extreme attack conditions, 256 attackers generating 100 Mbps each, the response time remained below 1.2 seconds. Increasing the complexity of the network had minimal impact as response times remained within a few hundred milliseconds, highlighting the scalability of the system. Lalropuia and Gupta [124] applied a Bayesian game theoretic model to cope with DoS attacks in small cell networks. The network availability at steady state ranged from 0.8185 to 0.9958 based on IDS detection probabilities, which emphasises the importance of detection sensitivity in maintaining service reliability under varying attack intensities.

Although these approaches differ in their architecture and attack focus, they have common goals: Minimizing latency, improving detection accuracy, and maintaining network availability. The REPEL framework is characterized by its efficiency at the control plane, while Mamolar's autonomous IDS provides a fast, fine-grained defense against attacks at the data plane. In contrast, the Bayesian model by Lalropuia and Gupta focuses on strategic defense decisions to maintain network availability.

2) Strategies to Mitigate Challenges in IDS-Based Approaches

IDS-based DDoS detection frameworks face challenges such as scalability, computational complexity, and adaptability in dynamic network environments. Several strategies have been proposed in the literature to solve these problems: (i) *Real-Time Detection and Response*: Mamolar et al. (2019) [122] emphasize the importance of near-instantaneous detection and mitigation through autonomic control loops that ensure rapid identification and neutralization of threats. (ii) *Scalability in Complex Topologies*: Mamolar et al. (2019) [123] demonstrated consistent detection performance despite increasing network complexity by using adaptive mechanisms to maintain response efficiency. (iii) *Minimizing*

Computational Overhead: Silva et al. (2020) [121] optimized signaling processes in the REPEL framework to reduce computational effort while maintaining detection accuracy, especially for control plane operations. (iv) *Adaptive Defense Strategies*: Lalropuia and Gupta (2020) [124] utilized a Bayesian approach to dynamically adjust IDS sensitivity based on perceived threats to improve network availability while efficiently allocating resources. (v) *Granular Mitigation Mechanisms*: Mamolar et al. (2019) [122] demonstrated the effectiveness of fine-grained mitigation at the user, tenant, or flow level, which enables precise isolation of malicious traffic without impacting legitimate users.

D. Hybrid Approach

These approaches combine the strengths of multiple approaches for maximum effectiveness. Even so, any redundant module can waste resources if not addressed carefully. It may also increase resource consumption and complexity and introduce issues like conflict, maintenance, and integration. Table 10 presents the overview of the hybrid strategies.

Iavich et al. [125] present a framework customized for 5G networks that integrated firewalls, IDS/IPS, and ML algorithms. While not specifically targeting DDoS attacks, the objective of the model is to evaluate its efficacy in identifying DoS/DDoS attacks. The test is done in a lab with a server and Raspberry Pi, and the results showcase the effectiveness of the model in identifying and reducing the impact of such attacks on 5G networks. Monge et al. propose a FlowSentinel intrusion detection approach [127] that detects DDoS attacks by extracting features from time series data and subsequently selecting the optimal prediction algorithm using a Random Forest classifier. Then, it uses a genetic algorithm to continuously recalibrate this algorithm and predict future traffic observations. Potential attacks are identified by comparing these predictions with real-time traffic data and flagging any notable deviations as suspicious.

Rawal et al. [128] propose a Split-Machine Learning System (Split-MLS) as a solution to the challenges and security requirements of 5G networks, specifically in detecting DDoS attacks. The Split-MLS combines ML algorithms with human intelligence to detect DDoS attacks by using packet timestamps and temporal features to classify network traffic as usual or malicious. The ML model is trained on a dataset of network traffic logs to detect DDoS attacks. As for the integration of human intelligence, an alert is sent to the admin to take the necessary steps after traffic is detected as malicious. According to the results of the experiments, the Split-MLS outperforms traditional ML models in terms of accuracy and false positive rate.

The paper [129] proposes a system consisting of multiple stakeholders in the network, each with their own management layer, that work together in a modular and autonomous way to detect and mitigate DDoS attacks. The system detects DDoS attacks through the use of a NIDS, supplemented by the Security Monitoring Agent (SMA), which monitors

TABLE 10. Hybrid Detection and Corresponding Defense in 5G/B5G

Ref	Functions	Detection	Defense	System Focus	Testbed/Tools	Dataset	Test Range	DDoS Attack
[125]	Identify, Protect, Detect, Respond	IDS-based, ML based, Signature-based	Traffic Blocking	5G	Raspberry Pi devices	Synthetic;KDD99 dataset: DOS1, (LDAP, MSSQL, NetBIOS, Syn, UDP, UDPLag), DOS2 (Portmap)	60 Raspberry Pi devices	Volumetric, Protocol, Application Layer
[126]	Identify, Protect, Detect, Respond	IDS based, ML based, Behavior-based	Adaptive Thresholding, Traffic Blocking	5G IoT	OVS, OpenDaylight (ODL) controller, NFV	Synthetic;Outgoing traffic captures from 62 different devices over 1, 3, and 5 days	62 network devices	Volumetric, Protocol, Application Layer
[127]	Identify, Detect, Respond	IDS based, ML based	x	5G IoT	OVS, ODL controller, NetFlow, Time Series Data Repository (TSDR), OpenStack.	Real traffic from 61 devices: 72,400 normal samples, 78,300 DDoS samples.	61 devices; data captured over 1, 3, and 5 days	Volumetric, Protocol
[128]	Identify, Protect, Detect, Respond	ML based	Traffic Blocking	5G/B5G IoT	DDoS stress testing software, Wireshark	Synthetic;5000 attack and non-attack packets generated using DDoS stress testing software.	Single victim host, multiple attacker hosts	Volumetric
[129]	Identify, Protect, Detect, Respond, Recover	5G Signature based, IDS-based	Traffic Blocking, Rule Enforcement	5G/6G IoT	CORE Emulator, OpenStack, Snort IDS, OpenAirInterface, RabbitMQ, MySQL, OVS, iproute2	Synthetic DDoS attack data generated using Bonesi for UDP flooding attacks.	4 to 256 attackers across different experiments.	Volumetric
[130]	Identify, Protect, Detect, Respond	ML based, Trust based	Traffic Blocking, Traffic Filtering Rules	5G IoT	x	Synthetic;100 attack sessions simulating DDoS attack patterns and 1000 normal sessions representing legitimate traffic.	1000 normal sessions, 100 attack sessions;	Volumetric, Protocol
[131]	Identify, Protect, Detect, Respond	ML-based, IDS based, Entropy-based	Traffic Blocking, Traffic Filtering	5G Standalone (SA) Core	Spirent Landslide 5G Traffic Generator, Apache Kafka, Redis memory DB	Synthetic data; Emulated traffic for attack scenarios	625,000 5G users for traffic data generation; 10 attack scenarios with 20-100 users per scenario.	Volumetric, Protocol, Application Layer
[132]	Identify, Protect, Detect, Respond, Recover	Signature-based, ML based	Traffic Blocking, Cost Increase, Blockchain-based Routing	5G	x	x	x	Volumetric, Protocol, Application Layer
[133]	Identify, Protect, Detect, Respond, Recover	Anomaly based, Entropy based	Traffic, blocking, Traffic orchestration	5G	OMNeT++, OVS	Synthetic data; Simulated traffic	60 UE nodes (20 benign, 40 malicious)	Volumetric
[134]	Identify, Protect, Detect, Respond, Recover	Anomaly based, ML based	Traffic blocking, Blacklisting	5G Network Slicing	OpenAirInterface my5G-RANTester	Synthetic data generated based on $\beta(3, 4)$ distribution	1000 MTC devices using the EURECOM 5G testbed	Volumetric

network traffic for unusual patterns. It combines traditional detection methods with specific insights into the 5G/6G network. When it spots something suspicious, it sends the traffic metrics and threat characteristics to the analyzer for a closer look. Marco *et al.* [126] propose a detection method for IoT-enabled 5G environments to identify the involvement of secured end users or devices in DDoS attacks. Their method analyzes traffic from 62 network devices with different behaviors. The approach examines source-side traffic flows to distinguish malicious traffic injections from ordinary activities. The proposal uses advanced feature extraction, pattern recognition, and adaptive thresholding. Detecting behavior inconsistencies and accurately classifying traffic can help identify protected devices or end users involved in DDoS attacks. On the other hand, a real-time DDoS defense framework based on multi-domain collaboration, combining information from multiple sources to detect attack sessions in 5G networks, is proposed in the paper [130]. It combines data from multiple sources to provide precise detection. Deep

packet inspection (DPI) is used to detect malicious traffic, while optimal packet sampling is used to reduce detection overhead. Additionally, it uses trust management, filtering rules, and session information to instantly categorize and stop attack traffic.

Park *et al.* [131] present a 5G Stand Alone Core Network DDoS detection system using ML classifiers like Bayesian, support vector machine, and random forest. Their approach involves preprocessing via entropy-based and statistics-based analyses, along with univariate feature selection using Chi-square and Analysis of variance F tests. While prior studies struggled with a 50-60% detection rate, their ML classifiers remarkably achieved an average accuracy of 98.7%. The proposed approach in [133] uses entropy as an initial metric to quantify the randomness of network traffic. It identifies abnormalities and subsequently categorizes them using a Self-Organizing Map (SOM) algorithm to detect DDoS attacks. A critical challenge can be the reliance on specific entropy thresholds, which can be easily influenced by sudden surges

TABLE 11. Overview of DDoS Detection Approaches in 5G/B5G

Detection	Pros	Cons	Accuracy	Scalability	Availability	CAPEX	OPEX
ML-based	High accuracy and adaptability	Requires large datasets and computing power; potential for false positives	High	Good	High	High	Moderate
Trust-based	Uses established trust metrics; Reduces false positives	Requires establishment and maintenance of trust relationships; potential trust calculation errors and manipulation; Limited in dynamic environments	Moderate	Variable	Moderate	Moderate	Moderate
IDS-based	Proven effectiveness; Established Technology	High complexity and resource-intensive	High	Moderate	High	Low	Low
Hybrid	Combines strengths of other approach; Enhance detection accuracy	Complex to implement and manage	Very High	Good	High	Very High	Variable

in traffic, potentially leading to incorrect identifications or missed detections in real-world scenarios. The proposed system in [134] detects DDoS attacks by monitoring the number of Attach Requests sent by MTC devices to the 5G core network, specifically to the AMF component. The upper bound of normal traffic during events is predicted by the system using a Gradient Boosting algorithm that has been trained using synthetic data that follows a $\beta(3, 4)$ probability distribution. The system determines whether each device is potentially malicious by calculating a detection rate if the observed traffic surpasses the predicted threshold.

Blockchain technology offers some unique capabilities such as decentralized security, immutable logging, automated responses via smart contracts, and more that show the potential for effective DDoS detection and Defense in 5G/6G networks. In the paper [132], a detection module is embedded into smart contracts within a blockchain network to identify DDoS attacks. This module analyzes data flow features, such as packet length and frequency, to classify traffic as benign or malicious. By training the detection model on samples released to the blockchain network, the system calculates confidence coefficients to indicate the likelihood of a DDoS attack, enabling proactive mitigation measures. While the system effectively addresses DoS/DDoS mitigation, the scalability of blockchain technology remains a challenge. The transaction fees and computational demands associated with processing substantial data volumes in 5G networks may result in bottlenecks, particularly during periods of intense network attacks. Moreover, the blockchain infrastructure itself can be susceptible to various attacks, including Sybil attacks and other forms of exploitation, necessitating further investigation.

1) Performance Analysis of Hybrid Approaches:

These studies aim to improve detection accuracy, reduce packet loss, and minimize latency. However, differences in protocols, detection algorithms and evaluation standards make a direct comparison difficult. (i) *Source-Side Detection Approaches*: Monge et al. [126] applied source-side DDoS detection to IoT-enabled 5G environments and achieved an AUC of 0.97 for synthetic web browsing and 0.96 for video streaming. Monge et al. [127] further developed FlowSentinel and achieved an AUC of 0.96, a TPR of 0.93, and an FPR of 0.01 at a granularity of 15 seconds. Performance decreased as the time window was adjusted, dropping to 0.88 at 7.5 seconds and 0.89 at 3 minutes, indicating sensitivity to the granularity of observation. (ii) *Machine Learning-Based Detection*: Iavich et al. [125] integrated machine learning into a firewall and IDS/IPS framework and achieved an accuracy of 96.11% on the KDD99 dataset, 99.37% on DOS1 and 99.99% on DOS2. The system excelled at detecting high-volume attacks such as Neptune and Guess_Password (100% accuracy), but struggled with low-volume attacks such as Rootkit (62%) and Spy (51%). Park et al. focused on DDoS signaling detection and used Naïve Bayesian, SVM and Random Forest algorithms to achieve a detection accuracy of 98.4%. This outperformed other studies targeting both 5G and earlier networks, where detection accuracy ranged from 53.8% to 91%.

(iii) *Multi-Layered and Hybrid Frameworks*: Sheibani et al. [133] proposed a multi-layered detection system that achieves a detection rate between 0.96 and 0.98 with false-positive rates from 5 to 50. The system maintained a packet loss rate of 0.01, outperforming Robust Security (RS) and SDN-Cloud Computing (SDN-CC), which had higher packet losses (0.22 and 0.42 for 10 OpenFlow switches). Benlloch-Caballero et al. [129] introduced a dual-layer system that achieves a detection rate of 78.12% and reduces the response

time from 57 to 18 seconds. (iv) *Advanced Collaborative Approaches*: Niboucha et al. [134] implemented zero-touch security management for mMTC network slices and achieved an accuracy of 96.76% for normal traffic and 83.63% for malicious traffic. Chen et al. [130] proposed a multidomain framework with a detection rate of 99%, while the packet inspection rate was reduced to 37% for attack sessions of more than ten packets. (v) *Hybrid Detection Systems with AI Integration*: Rawal et al. [128] proposed a Split-Machine Learning System combining automated detection with human supervision and achieving near-perfect detection for HTTP and TCP traffic. However, detection of UDP traffic was less accurate due to its connectionless nature. Fang et al. [132] integrated blockchain with AI to mitigate DDoS attacks, but the computational overhead led to latency and limited real-time detection capabilities.

2) Challenges and Mitigation Strategies in Hybrid Approaches

Hybrid DDoS detection approaches in 5G networks face several interconnected challenges for which some solutions exist in the literature: (i) *Coordination Complexity*: The synchronization of detection layers complicates the interaction between infrastructure and service providers. Standardized communication protocols and centralized coordination mechanisms can mitigate this [129]. (ii) *Scalability Issues*: Manual monitoring limits scalability in dynamic 5G environments. The inclusion of automated decision-making processes and adaptive machine learning models can address this [128]. (iii) *Latency Concerns*: Blockchain integration leads to latency times due to computational overhead. Optimizing blockchain protocols and incorporating lightweight detection mechanisms can improve real-time responsiveness [132]. (iv) *Adaptability to Evolving Threats*: Reliance on predefined traffic patterns hinders the detection of novel attacks. The use of self-learning, adaptive algorithms that evolve with emerging threats improves adaptability [134]. (v) *Detection of Stealthy Attacks*: Although effective in detecting large-scale attacks, some frameworks remain untested for stealthy threats. Combining anomaly detection with signature-based methods increases sensitivity to subtle attacks [130]. (vi) *Resource Efficiency*: Complex processing requires resources. The implementation of resource-efficient algorithms and the use of cloud-based processing create a balance between computing requirements and real-time detection needs [128], [132].

In Summary, Table 11 shows the overview of these detection approaches. Please note that this table provides mainly qualitative information, as the quantitative comparison is impractical due to the inconsistency of datasets, metrics, and experimental environments throughout the reviewed literature. *In terms of scalability*, ML-based systems are generally high due to their learning capabilities and continuous adaptation to new threats, but they can

be affected by the quality and quantity of training data. Trust-based systems have medium accuracy since they may not recognize sophisticated attacks designed to appear as legitimate traffic. IDS tends to have high accuracy when configured correctly. However, this varies with network conditions. Hybrid systems can achieve a very high level of accuracy due to their comprehensive approach to detection. *In terms of accuracy*, ML-based systems are generally high due to their learning capabilities and continuous adaptation to new threats, as firewall rules can be easily distributed and applied across different network segments, making them suitable for both small and large networks. However, it can be affected by the quality and quantity of training data. Trust-based systems have medium accuracy since they may not recognize sophisticated attacks designed to appear as legitimate traffic. IDS tends to have high accuracy when configured correctly. However, this varies with network conditions. Hybrid systems can achieve a very high level of accuracy due to their comprehensive approach to detection. *In terms of global availability*, some of the methods are emerging, while others are still limited. However, all of the approaches are available globally. For instance, Google's TensorFlow is utilized in DDoS detection systems to analyze network traffic patterns and identify anomalies, leveraging ML's ability to adapt to evolving threats. Blockchain-based systems like the Nebula network assign trust levels to nodes, using these trust scores to detect and prevent malicious activities within the network. Snort, an open-source IDS, is widely used for real-time traffic analysis and packet logging, detecting known attack patterns through signature matching. Cisco's Talos intelligence group combines signature-based, anomaly-based, and ML-based techniques to provide comprehensive threat detection and response, an example of a hybrid detection approach. *In terms of capital expenditures (CAPEX) and Operational expenditures (OPEX)*, ML-based detection involves high CAPEX for initial setup, including hardware, software, and expertise. OPEX is moderate, covering ongoing model updates and maintenance as it automates the process. Trust-based detection methods have moderate CAPEX and OPEX. Initial costs are associated with implementing the trust framework, while ongoing costs involve monitoring and adjusting trust levels. IDS-based detection methods typically have low CAPEX and OPEX due to their standardized and mature technology, requiring minimal setup and maintenance. Hybrid detection methods involve high CAPEX for the initial integration of various systems and moderate OPEX for ongoing management and updates.

IV. DDoS Attack Defense in B5G

The effectiveness of defense approaches depends heavily on DDoS detection, as inaccurate detection can compromise legitimate traffic. These approaches are categorized as follows.

A. Traffic Blocking Based Approaches

The paper [119] proposes an access-side defense architecture to defend against DDoS attacks in Space-Air-Ground Integrated 6G V2X networks. A seamless network edge defense perimeter is created by an access-side control point and local controllers at the network edge. The local controllers use lightweight detection methods to determine the type and intensity of attacks and work together to control traffic and ensure a consistent defense. The access-side control points apply filtering rules to block attack traffic and enforce access authentication. The system achieves high efficiency and scalability in the simulation results.

In [135], the multi-access edge computing (MEC) layer of the proposed system responds to attacks by enabling security features such as device authentication, access restriction, and data encryption. Suspicious actions are kept safe, and malicious behavior leads to immediate deactivation of the suspicious device to mitigate the attack. In the paper [130], the proposed system deploys defense mechanisms at the source of the 5G network to prevent malicious traffic from entering the data network. It utilizes real-time filtering rules and session management to immediately stop attack traffic and integrates trust management to continuously assess and block traffic from compromised IoT devices. The defense process presented in [136] includes blocking malicious packets at the controller level and instructing OpenFlow switches to stop processing packets from the detected malicious UE.

The paper [137] proposes a defense mechanism against UDP DrDoS (distributed reflection DoS) attacks, the IEWA (Increasing Expense and Weak Authentication) scheme. This scheme is designed to improve the security of UDP-based protocols that are vulnerable to DrDoS attacks, such as the Network Time Protocol (NTP). The IEWA scheme uses client-server authentication to verify requests and prevent spoofed or malicious traffic from overloading the server. The system indirectly blocks legitimate user traffic to reduce DrDoS attacks by adding authentication measures that increase attackers' computational costs while maintaining system availability for legitimate users. The system proposed in [134] implements a decision engine (DE) that evaluates the detection rate of the Gradient Boosting algorithm for mitigation purposes. If the detection rate of a device exceeds a predetermined threshold, the system disconnects the device from the network and adds it to a blacklist, thereby preventing future access. By isolating and disabling the devices that are responsible for the abnormal traffic, this process effectively mitigates the impact of the DDoS attack.

B. Traffic Orchestration Based Approaches

Sattar et al. [138] present a strategy to mitigate DDoS attacks targeting 5G core network slicing. Their proposal focuses on the use of slice isolation as a means of strengthening network security and maintaining availability. To achieve this, they develop a mathematical model that enables on-demand slice isolation and aims to guarantee end-to-end delay while effec-

tively mitigating DDoS threats within the 5G network slicing infrastructure. The paper [139] introduces a G/M/1 model for edge server task scheduling to improve load balancing between edge servers, and the experimental results validate the effectiveness of this method. In [140], a comprehensive DNTM (Dynamic Network Traffic Management) system is proposed for DDoS mitigation within the ISP domain. This system includes components such as an attack detector, an IP prioritizer, a traffic manager, and a Netflow classifier. The Netflow classifier achieves an average recall, precision, and F1 score of over 96% when tested on datasets containing UDP flood, ICMP flood, and TCP flood attacks.

In the manuscript at [141], ProDefense is proposed as an active DDoS defense framework based on SDN. The ProDefense framework includes application-specific network traffic threshold standards. In order to avoid controller failures, this framework uses a distributed controller platform that enables load balancing. Compared to other applications with different requirements and expectations regarding network disruptions and service tolerance, ProDefense provides consistency across all controllers, resulting in fast and consistent response times. One example is F5 Networks, which distributes incoming network traffic to different servers. Candal-Ventureira et al. [142] propose an SDN-based architecture to identify suspicious nodes in 5G networks, focusing in particular on IoT devices. In this architecture, traffic from designated nodes is redirected to a secondary network slice, where it is carefully analyzed before it can reach its actual destination. The compatibility and ease of integration into existing 5G networks are remarkable and offer a potential solution for the efficient quarantine of suspicious IoT devices. A different methodology, MTDNS, is introduced in [143] specifically for mitigating DDoS attacks on Domain Name Server (DNS) servers. It employs Moving Target Defense (MTD) techniques through SDN switches to redirect traffic to dynamically generated alternative DNS servers operating within the NFV framework, thereby reducing the risk of legitimate packet loss.

C. Hybrid Approaches

DDoS defense mechanisms in 5G focus on mitigating the impact of DDoS attacks to ensure the availability and reliability of 5G network services, and they include a range of proactive strategies and reactive measures. There are many different types of DDoS defense mechanisms based on purely SDN. Commonly used mitigation strategies include: redirecting traffic [144] [145], blocking ports [145] [146], and dropping packets [147] [148]. Other defenses based on SDN include traffic isolation, deep packet checking, and changing MAC and IP addresses [145] [146]. These defense strategies are a bit outdated, and since technology has advanced so much thanks to machine learning, such technologies have also been used to detect and mitigate DDoS attacks. The authors [149], for example, have used machine learning to detect and mitigate DDoS attacks with 96% accuracy. Hybrid approaches,

TABLE 12. Defense Focused Approaches in 5G/B5G

Ref	Functions	Detection	Defense	System Focus	Testbed/Tools	Dataset	Test Range	DDoS Attack
[135]	Identify, Protect, Detect, Respond, Recover	ML-based	Traffic Blocking, Limiting Access	5G IoT	x	Real log activity of a mobile health application	x	Volumetric, Protocol, Application Layer
[137]	Identify, Protect, Detect, Respond, Recover	x	Access Authentication, Cost increase, Traffic Filtering.	5G	Windows 7 under VMware (NTP server); Ubuntu (running scripts)	Simulated UDP requests and responses, particularly focusing on NTP DrDoS attacks	x	Protocol
[136]	Identify, Protect, Detect, Respond, Recover	Threshold-based	Traffic Blocking	SDN-based 5G	OMNET++.	100 network realizations, each with 50-second runtime, 60 UEs.	Up to 60 UEs (20 benign, 40 malicious).	Volumetric
[138]	Identify, Protect, Detect, Respond, Recover	x	Traffic Orchestration, Mathematical Model, Slice Isolation	5G Core Network Slicing	OpenVZ, AMPL, CPLEX, Linux Traffic control, ns3 with mmWave module	Traffic traces collected from ns3 simulations	6 physical servers (3 for slice allocation, 2 for DDoS nodes, 1 client)	Volumetric
[139]	Identify, Protect, Detect, Respond	x	Traffic Orchestration, G/M/I Queuing Model	5G ultradense, and MEC	x	Real dataset from Central Business District (CBD) of Melbourne	125 service base stations, 816 random users	Volumetric
[140]	Identify, Protect, Detect, Respond, Recover	EL based, Statistics-based	Ingress/Egress Filtering, Rate Limiting, Traffic Orchestration	5G	BoNeSi, Apache Spark, Minisom, Ubuntu Linux (cluster computing)	Synthetic datasets combining legitimate ISP traffic and spoofed IP addresses generated by BoNeSi. Real UDP flood attack data from online game tournament	Real customer network traffic and simulated attack traffic.	Volumetric, Protocol
[142]	Identify, Protect, Detect, Respond	DPI-based, Threshold-based	Traffic Redirection, Traffic Blocking	SDN based 4G/5G IoT	OpenAirInterface, OVS, ONOS SDN controller, Docker containers	Simulated traffic patterns of various IoT devices in factory automation scenarios	Up to 250 devices per flow	Volumetric, Protocol, Application Layer

such as that in [150], propose a combination of anomaly and misuse detection. Another major advance in technology is the use of AI in applications. This has led to some research interest in using AI to detect DDoS attacks. The authors in [151] give an overview of the AI algorithms used to classify and detect DDoS attacks. These algorithms include Naive Bayes, Support Vector Machine, and Random Forest Tree. Another study [152] presents a progressive transfer learning method based on deep networks that enables the throttling of routers to cope with DDoS attacks.

After detecting a DoS attack, the proposed defense mechanism in [124] employs a Bayesian game model to capture the interactions between the attacker (the mobile user) and the defender of the network, i.e., the IDS-equipped small cell base stations. The game model makes it easier to determine optimal strategies for both the attacker and the defender to mitigate the effects of the attack. The defenders have the choice of defending against the attack or not defending. Defense includes actively monitoring the network for suspicious activity and alerting the system administrator with true-positive rates indicating successful attack detection. By dynamically adapting defense strategies based on the attacker's behavior and network conditions, the proposed defense mechanism aims to minimize the impact of DoS attacks on network availability and performance.

To achieve mitigation, the framework proposed in [133] utilizes a Double Deep Q-Network (DDQN) to manage and relocate OpenFlow switches across distributed controllers.

The purpose of this reallocation is to equitably distribute the network load and avoid any one controller from becoming a bottleneck, thereby mitigating the effect of a DDoS attack. On the other hand, upon detecting an attack, the system in [116] initiates a proactive and reactive mitigation procedure. At first, the system effectively blocks harmful traffic at the MEC level, thus preventing it from overpowering the V2X aggregator. Concurrently, the framework enhances the network's reaction by modifying the RAN to prohibit malevolent cars from accessing the network. These vehicles are then redirected to restricted cells that have limited or no communication capabilities. This well-coordinated and multi-faceted strategy guarantees that the DDoS attack is confined not only to the local MEC but also to the wider network infrastructure, hence reducing any disturbance to crucial V2X services. Table 12 encompasses defense-focused strategies that do not center on detection.

In summary, Table 13 shows the empirical overview of these defense approaches. *In terms of effectiveness,* traffic blocking methods are moderately effective because they block malicious traffic directly at the network edge. They are quick to implement but can inadvertently disrupt legitimate traffic if not carefully managed. Orchestration methods are very effective as they coordinate and redirect malicious traffic to alternative paths, minimizing the impact on legitimate services and maintaining overall network availability. Hybrid mitigation methods are very effective as they combine different strategies, such as blocking, redirection, and traffic

TABLE 13. DDoS Mitigation Approaches in 5G/B5G

Mitigation	Pros	Cons	Effectiveness	Scalability	Availability	CAPEX	OPEX
Traffic Blocking	Immediate response; Simple to implement	Can block legitimate traffic	High for known threats	Good	High	Low	Low for known threat
Traffic Orchestration	Intelligently manages traffic flow for optimized performance and security; Diverts malicious traffic away from target; Reduces load on primary servers	High complexity; Requires advanced technology and significant infrastructure; Potential delays in response	High	Good	High	High	High
Hybrid	Combines multiple mitigation techniques for comprehensive protection	Complex to implement and manage	High	Good	High	High	High

shaping, to comprehensively combat different attack vectors. *In terms of scalability*, traffic blocking methods are highly scalable because firewall rules can be easily distributed and applied to different network segments, making them suitable for both small and large networks. Orchestration methods are highly scalable as they can distribute traffic across multiple paths and data centers, ensuring effective mitigation even for large-scale attacks. Hybrid mitigation methods are highly scalable and enable the integration and coordination of multiple techniques to cope with increasing traffic volumes and complex attacks.

In terms of global availability, DDoS blocking solutions, such as those implemented by Cloudflare, provide comprehensive global coverage. These systems are designed to work across a geographically distributed network, allowing them to effectively block malicious requests from different locations around the world. Orchestration methods, such as those used by Akamai, Cloudflare, or IBM, also have high global availability. Hybrid mitigation methods, such as Akamai’s Kona Site Defender, are widely used and combine the strengths of different techniques supported by leading cybersecurity vendors to provide comprehensive protection. *In terms of CAPEX and OPEX*, traffic block methods are typically associated with low CAPEX and OPEX due to their simplicity and ease of implementation, with minimal ongoing maintenance required. Orchestration methods can require high CAPEX for initial setup with moderate OPEX for ongoing management and coordination. Hybrid mitigation methods require high CAPEX for integrating different techniques and moderate OPEX for maintaining and optimizing the system.

Table 14 suggests how 5G/5G-A mitigation strategies might evolve to address potential DDoS threats in 6G [153] extending Table 4. While 6G-specific threats remain largely hypothetical, each adaptation is grounded in existing methods, providing a probable framework for how current technologies might evolve. The aim here is exploratory, sug-

gesting viable paths forward rather than definitive solutions.

D. Industry Efforts in DDoS Mitigation for 5G and Beyond

To align this survey with real-world implementations and industry standards, we have included insights from ongoing efforts by leading standardization bodies and organizations that can help with DDoS mitigation in 5G and beyond networks. The 3rd Generation Partnership Project (3GPP), particularly in its Release 17 [164], has introduced improved security mechanisms such as the Service Communication Proxy (SCP) and the Network Data Analytics Function (NWDAF). SCP helps load balance and throttle service requests, which can help prevent network congestion typical of DDoS attacks. NWDAF provides data-driven insights by analyzing network behavior in real time. Although the primary goal of NWDAF is network optimization, it plays a critical role in anomaly detection by identifying abnormal traffic patterns indicative of DDoS attacks, enabling proactive mitigation of the threat. Recent efforts by 3GPP underscore the industry’s commitment to DDoS mitigation in 5G networks. A contribution at the 3GPP TSG-SA3 Meeting #115 in [165] highlights the security risks posed by dedicated User Plane Functions (UPFs) interacting with PLMNs via the N4 interface. Improved protection measures, such as hiding the mutual topology and mitigating DDoS attacks at the interface level, are proposed. Similarly, a proposal from Huawei and HiSilicon at the 3GPP TSG-SA3 Meeting #94 proposes a RAN-based DDoS mitigation strategy. It uses the NWDAF to detect malicious User Equipment (UEs) and blacklist them in the RAN to prevent resource exhaustion [166]. These initiatives reflect growing industry recognition of DDoS vulnerabilities in 5G’s distributed architecture and the need for proactive security measures. Industry leaders like Nokia and NetScout [167] have also developed AI-powered solutions. Nokia has introduced advanced DDoS mitigation solutions to address the growing complexity of attacks in 5G, IoT and cloud-connected networks. In

TABLE 14. Exploratory Adaptations of 5G/5G-A Mitigation Strategies for Potential DDoS Threats in 6G

6G Technology	Potential DDoS Threat	Relevant 5G/5G-A Mitigation Approaches	Potential 6G-Adaption
Quantum Communication [62], [63], [65]–[69]	Physical channel disruption, noise induction	ML-based anomaly detection, rapid traffic blocking	AI-enhanced noise filtering, dynamic quantum key refresh
THz Communications [70]–[75]	Cross-network DDoS via weak encryption	Trust-based IDS, adaptive encryption protocols	AI-based traffic analysis, adaptive lightweight encryption
OWC [76]–[78]	Receiver overload, congestion	ML-based IDS with congestion management	Edge ML congestion control, real-time traffic load balancing
Edge Intelligence [76]–[78]	Service overload, resource constraints	Trust-based IDS with resource monitoring, rate limiting	Predictive resource allocation, ML-enhanced anomaly detection
Blockchain Technology [81]–[85]	Transaction flooding, memory pool exhaustion	ML-based trust analytics	Enhanced consensus protocols, adaptive rate limiting, AI-enhanced trust management to mitigate transaction overload
NTN [86]–[89]	Satellite flooding, resource exhaustion	Hybrid IDS with adaptive monitoring	Satellite-specific adaptive IDS, prioritized traffic routing for efficient resource management
ZSM [91]–[93]	Parameter exploitation, API vulnerabilities	ML-based IDS with API security	Tokenized API security, multi-layered defenses, ML-powered trust assessments for service integrity
O-RAN [94], [94]–[96]	Modular vulnerabilities, software updates	Hybrid IDS with access control	Automated software patching with AI-driven vulnerability assessments, fine-grained access control for modular security

2024, Nokia introduced its enhanced Defender Mitigation System (7750 DMS-1) [168], equipped with an Advanced Countermeasures Engine (ACE) that provides stateful L4-L7 inspection to combat volumetric, botnet and application layer attacks. At the core of this solution is the AI-driven Deepfield Defender, which analyzes network data in real time to efficiently detect and neutralize threats. Features such as global DDoS botnet mapping, DNS protection and geo-IP blocking ensure robust DDoS defense in modern networks.

V. Experimental Datasets, Tools and Technologies

This paper studies various research efforts that employed distinct testbeds and datasets to explore strategies for mitigating DDoS attacks in 5G/B5G networks. The tools utilized in DDoS experiments within mobile networks, particularly those referenced in this reviewed literature are primarily classified into simulation tools and platforms, real testbed tools and platforms, and traffic generation and analysis tools. Additional categories of supporting tools encompass networking and SDN technologies, along with virtualization and containerization tools. The computational resources accessible to the researcher, together with a discussion on the B5G/6G testbed, are also presented at the end of the section. Fig. 6 illustrates the utilization of some commonly used tools

for studying DDoS mitigation in cellular infrastructure. The tools listed in this section are referenced in Tables 5-10 and 12.

A. Simulation Tools and Platforms

These platforms allow researchers to simulate and study the behavior and performance of cellular networks and provide a virtual controlled environment for testing algorithms and settings. Some tools are used together to build a complete simulation environment. For instance, *UERANSIM* and *Open5GS* are commonly utilized for the simulation of 5G network environments [102], [103]. *UERANSIM* serves as an open-source simulator for 5G networks, while *Open5GS* provides a comprehensive implementation of a 5G core network. Together, they provide a realistic simulation environment that supports various setups and facilitates a diverse array of experiments, including DDoS Mitigation. These tools provide flexibility and accurately simulate real-life scenarios. *OASIM* is a simulation platform developed by the OpenAirInterface (OAI) project, designed for the simulation of 4G and 5G networks. This enables researchers to evaluate and verify network protocols and configurations within a controlled virtual environment, simulating actual network conditions without the need for physical hardware

TABLE 15. Simulation Platforms for Cellular Networks

Tool	Type	Programming Language	Platform Compatibility	5G RAN Support	5G Core Support	B5G Support	Real Testbed Support	Scalability	5G Feature Support (Native/Requires Extension)
ns-3 [138], [154]	Network Simulator	C++	Linux, Windows, macOS	Yes	Yes	Limited	Limited	High	Slicing (5G-LENA), mmWave (ns3-mmwave), MEC (TeraSim), IoT (NB-IoT)
OMNeT++ [136], [155], [156]	Network Simulator	C++	Linux, Windows, macOS	Yes	Yes	Limited	No	High	Slicing (via Simu5G), MEC (via Simu5G), IoT (INET)
Simu5G [155], [156]	OMNeT++ 5G NR library	C++	Linux, Windows	Yes	Limited	No (Potential)	No	High	RAN Slicing, MEC (ETSI MEC model), mmWave (part of 5G NR)
srsRAN [157], [158]	LTE/5G RAN Emulator	C	Linux	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	Mid	Slicing, IoT (NB-IoT Signalling)
OpenAir-Interface (OAI) [129], [142]	5G Network Emulator/ Real Testbed	C/C++	Linux	Yes	Yes	Yes (Limited)	Yes	High	Slicing (partially) NTN [159]
OAISim [121]	OAI Simulator Mode	C/C++	Linux	Yes	Limited	Limited	No	Mid	Slicing (partially)
FlexRAN [108]	RAN Controller Emulator	C++	Linux	Yes	Limited	Limited	Limited	High	RAN Slicing (via extensions)
Open5GS [102], [103]	5G Core Emulator	C	Linux	No	Yes	No	Yes	Mid	Core Network Slicing
UERANSIM [102], [103], [158]	5G RAN Simulator	C++	Linux	Yes	No	No	No	High	Network Slicing
CORE [122], [123], [129]	Network Emulator	Python, C++	Linux, Windows	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	High	Network Slicing, MEC (requires custom config)
SGSNEmu [123]	Emulator	C++	Linux	No	Yes	No	Yes	Mid	2G/3G Focused
Mininet [160], [161]	Network Emulator	Python	Linux	No	No	Limited	No	High	Slicing (via SDN Controller)
NetSim [162], [163]	Network Simulator	C++	Linux, Windows, macOS	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	High	Network Slicing, MEC, mmWave, IoT

FIGURE 6. Tools for DDoS Mitigation in Cellular Infrastructure

deployment. CORE (Common Open Research Emulator) serves as a lightweight emulator designed for the creation of virtual networks, frequently utilized in the testing of SDN and NFV. SGSNemu is a GPRS/UMTS (3G) network emulator designed to simulate the functionality of the Serving GPRS Support Node (SGSN) in mobile networks. The focus is primarily on 2G and 3G networks, making it beneficial for testing and development within those contexts. NetSim serves as a network simulation and emulation tool, facilitating the modeling of diverse network types, including 5G networks. This tool simulates network behavior, analyzes performance metrics, and tests new protocols or network configurations across wired, wireless, and mobile networks. The system supports 5G NR, flexible modeling, SDN, and network slicing, making it appropriate for B5G and 6G research. ns-3 and Mininet are prominent open-source tools utilized for network simulation and emulation. ns-3 serves as a tool for simulating the performance of the Internet and communication networks, encompassing 4G, 5G, and future technologies, supported by its comprehensive libraries for Wi-Fi, LTE, 5G NR, and various other network standards. Mininet serves as a lightweight network emulator, suitable for the development, testing, and deployment of SDN applications, as well as for experimentation with network slicing and NFV in the context of 5G and future networks. OMNeT++ serves as an open-source framework for discrete-event simulation, extensively utilized for modeling various types of networks, including wired, wireless, and mobile networks, along with other distributed systems.

Tools such as OAISIM, Open5GS, and UERANSIM are designed specifically for mobile networks. In contrast, other widely used tools such as ns-3, OMNeT++, and Mininet

were originally developed for general-purpose network simulation, which includes wired networks. These tools have been extended with libraries and modules to accommodate 5G/B5G use cases, such as network slicing⁷ and mmWave⁸, rendering them useful for early-stage primary experiments in B5G/6G. Table 15 presents a comparative table for widely used simulation platforms.

B. Real Testbed Tools and Platforms

Unlike simulators and emulators, with a real testbed, the physical environment is replicated, ensuring all aspects of network performance. Wireless networks operate in unpredictable environments with real-world challenges like obstructions, weather conditions, and mobility. A real testbed captures these conditions, ensuring more realistic and actionable results, whereas simulators approximate these factors with models that may not fully capture their variability and impact.

OpenAirInterface is an open-source software platform that supports both 4G and 5G RAN as well as core networks. *FlexRAN*, a customizable controller for RAN, enables real-time communication and provides practical insights into real-world applications. These tools offer a wide range of customization options and the flexibility to scale up, making them suitable for conducting in-depth network experiments. OpenAirInterface and FlexRAN can be utilized together in 5G research [108]. *srsRAN* is an Open-source software suite for building 4G/5G mobile networks, including both RAN and core network elements. It can be used in real testbeds as well as for simulation or emulation purposes, allowing users to deploy, test, and experiment with LTE/5G networks in both software-defined radio (SDR) setups and virtualized environments.

C. Traffic Generation and Analysis

Traffic generators enable network researchers and engineers to generate and analyze traffic in a controlled environment. These tools generate network traffic for testing purposes, enabling researchers to evaluate networks' performance and resilience under various load conditions.

iPerf [108] is a commonly utilized tool for doing active measurements to determine the maximum attainable bandwidth on IP networks. This tool is programmed in C, is user-friendly, and is compatible with numerous platforms, rendering it optimal for producing network traffic to evaluate DDoS defenses. Nevertheless, its main focus is on evaluating bandwidth, and it may not encompass all forms of network traffic. *Metasploit* and *Mausezahn* [108] are well-known tools in the field of traffic generation. Mausezahn is particularly useful for stress testing and simulating DDoS attacks, while Metasploit is a powerful penetration testing framework. It is used to develop and execute exploit code on remote targets. These tools produce authentic attack scenarios, which are important

⁷<https://networksimulationtools.com/network-slicing-simulation/>

⁸<https://omnet-manual.com/how-to-implement-mmwave-in-omnet/>

for evaluating network defenses. When used together, they provide a wide range of DDoS testing situations, which is helpful for security research. However, the complex setup of Metasploit and the hardware constraints of Mausezahn can provide difficulties. In addition, several other *DDoS stress testing software tools* [128], such as LOIC and HOIC [169], can be used to simulate DDoS attacks. These technologies are easy to use and effective for conducting stress tests.

BoNeSi [123], [129], [140] is a simulator for replicating network traffic and DDoS attacks. This open-source application, developed in the C programming language, is specifically tailored for conducting DDoS simulations. Nevertheless, its capabilities are restricted to DDoS situations, and configuring it might be difficult. The *Spirent Landslide 5G Traffic Generator* [131] is a widely utilized commercial tool in the market for generating traffic to test the effectiveness of DDoS defenses in 5G networks. It provides precision and is compatible with extensive testing, albeit it comes at a considerable cost and necessitates a commercial license. There are more traffic generator tools out there such as *Ostinato* [170], *TRex*, *Pktgen-DPDK* [171] which are widely used by researcher.

Following traffic generation, the most crucial phase is its analysis. There are frameworks and tools that help analyze network performance, monitor traffic, detect intrusions, and process large datasets. *Wireshark* [128] is a widely used tool for analyzing network protocols, coded in the C language. It offers comprehensive support for various protocols and has advanced features for analyzing data. It enables in-depth inspection of network traffic and is, therefore, essential for DDoS detection. On the other hand, *Snort* [129] is a freely available system for detecting and preventing unauthorized access to computer networks. Snort, which was developed in the C programming language, is widely used for instant identification and defense against DDoS attacks. The NIDS tool is important and widely used in network security because it is effective, user-friendly, and can work in real-time. Nevertheless, it can provide inaccurate results and requires careful customization to achieve the desired results.

Some other tools are commonly used, but these are not used in the paper reviewed in this study. For example, *Scapy* [172] is a powerful Python package that is commonly used for manipulating and analyzing network packets but is not used in the reviewed papers. The versatility and seamless integration with Python make it ideal for customized network analysis and DDoS research. In addition, *Tcpreplay* [173] is a collection of open-source tools coded in C specifically designed for modifying and replaying previously collected network traffic. Testing DDoS mitigation measures against real traffic scenarios is an efficient approach. Although this tool has its advantages, it is limited to the playback of previously recorded network data and requires the availability of such data for analysis. *Elasticsearch* [174], implemented in Java, is a distributed search and analysis engine that follows the RESTful architectural style. It has robust search

capabilities and real-time analytics, making it well-suited for exploring and analyzing data in DDoS detection.

D. Networking and SDN Tools

In the context of 5G/6G networks and DDoS mitigation, Networking and SDN tools play an important role in managing, controlling, and optimizing network traffic. *Open vSwitch (OVS)* [126], [127] is a C-based virtual switch that works on many layers and is designed for virtual machines (VMs) and containers. OVS is suitable for efficient traffic redirection in virtualized environments and offers a high level of control over network topologies and traffic generation. OVS also has a high degree of adaptability and is compatible with a wide range of protocols. *OpenDaylight* [126], [127], an SDN controller platform, is also implemented in Java and aims to accelerate the adoption of SDN while providing a robust foundation for NFV. OpenDaylight offers flexibility and is compatible with multiple network protocols, making it well-suited for managing SDN setups to defend against DDoS attacks.

ONOS [142], an open-source SDN network operating system, is developed with Java and is specifically designed for high availability, performance, and scalability. ONOS is well-suited for managing SDN environments for DDoS defense since it can handle large-scale operations and is compatible with various SDN applications. However, similar to OpenDaylight, it requires complex configuration and a comprehensive understanding of SDN principles. *Traffic Control (tc)* [138] is a C-based Linux program used for network capacity management, congestion avoidance, and traffic control. *Tc* is extremely customizable and offers a range of traffic control features, making it an indispensable tool for effectively regulating network traffic during DDoS attacks. However, its use is limited to Linux environments. *Iproute2* [129], developed in C, is a set of tools for managing TCP/IP networks and controlling traffic on Linux. It provides robust networking technologies often used in Linux environments for DDoS mitigation.

E. Development and Data Science Tools

Python or *MATLAB* are often used for simulating 5G DDoS experiments due to the ease of integration, flexibility and control [109], [110], [112], [113], [115], [117]. Python-based environments using libraries such as *Scikit-learn*, *Pandas*, *TensorFlow*, and *NumPy* provide versatile and user-friendly frameworks for simulating networks and analyzing data. These libraries are often used to quickly create prototypes and perform experiments. They are helpful for tasks such as creating models, analyzing data, and visualizing results. Nevertheless, such simulations cannot have the same level of realism as specialized programs such as UERANSIM and Open5GS. In addition, performance may be limited by the processing capacity of the utilized machine. Although there are some limitations, Python-based tools can seamlessly

interface with many frameworks and offer flexible options for network research.

Keras [114], [119] along with MATLAB are analysis frameworks widely employed for data analysis and training machine learning models. MATLAB offers a wide range of tools for developing algorithms, analyzing data, and visualizing information, while Keras simplifies the process of constructing and training neural networks. These technologies are well-suited for performing complicated statistical analysis and creating predictive models, making them indispensable for security research. Nevertheless, MATLAB is known for its high costs, and both MATLAB and Keras place high demands on computing power, especially for complex DL tasks. Although it comes at an additional cost, integrating these technologies with network simulators can provide valuable insights into network security. As a solution to the resource limitation, **Google Colab** [114], [115] is a free cloud utility that allows AI developers to run Jupyter notebooks in the cloud. As it provides unrestricted access to GPUs and TPUs, it is an optimal platform for developing and testing ML models for DDoS detection. On the other hand, it is dependent on an internet connection and offers restricted customization options.

F. Virtualization and Containerization Tools

When conducting experiments and implementing DDoS defense techniques on a larger scale in test environments, limited resources are a major challenge. To test and mitigate DDoS and create scalable application environments, virtualization and containerization technologies are essential. **Docker** [142] is a Go platform that allows users to build, deploy and run applications in containers. Docker is perfect for creating and implementing solutions to mitigate distributed denial of service attacks because it is portable and easy to use. Docker also helps researchers to overcome the problem of limited resources. The open-source platform **Kubernetes** [175] uses Go to automate the process of deploying, scaling, and managing containerized applications. Kubernetes is perfect for automating container management for DDoS defense, as it is scalable and supports multiple applications.

OpenVZ [138], developed in C, is a container-based virtualization solution for Linux that creates multiple secure, isolated Linux containers on a single physical server. Virtualizing environments for DDoS testing is a good solution for OpenVZ because it is lightweight and uses resources efficiently. **OpenStack** [121], [127], [129] is a Python-based open source software platform that is often used for Infrastructure-as-a-Service (IaaS) deployments in the cloud. For DDoS studies, OpenStack is the way to go due to its scalability and the many services it offers. The Ruby-based **Vagrant** [175] is a platform for creating and managing portable virtual environments for software development. Creating portable environments for DDoS testing is facilitated by Vagrant because it is user-friendly and supports multiple

vendors. Virtualizing computing environments for DDoS research is made easy with **VMware vSphere** [176], a cloud computing virtualization technology that is both proprietary and offers a wide range of features. Although vSphere is cost-effective and commonly used in organizations, it requires specialized expertise to work well.

G. Testbed vs. Simulation for DDoS Mitigation in 5G/B5G Networks

Evaluating DDoS detection and mitigation strategies in 5G and beyond requires methodologies that accurately reflect real-world network behavior, hardware variability, and adversarial attack adaptations. While simulations provide a controlled environment for algorithm testing, they often fail to capture dynamic traffic behaviors and real-time network constraints observed in operational 5G systems.

Testbeds enable real-time validation of security frameworks under dynamic conditions, offering critical insights into performance, scalability, and resilience. Unlike simulations, which rely on predefined parameters, testbeds capture unpredictable network variations, making them essential for benchmarking adaptive attack behaviors, network congestion effects, and mitigation responses [177]. For instance, studies on 5G network slices have demonstrated that hardware-induced variability can significantly impact detection efficiency, an aspect that simulations often fail to replicate. Similarly, real-time 5G testbeds have revealed latency fluctuations and resource allocation challenges that influence the effectiveness of DDoS mitigation techniques. Key advantages of testbed-based evaluations over simulations include [177], [178]:

Hardware Variability Impact: Testbeds allow researchers to analyze real-world deviations in latency, packet loss, and resource constraints that affect DDoS detection efficiency. Unlike simulations, which assume ideal conditions, testbeds reveal hardware-induced performance degradation in detection mechanisms.

Adaptive Security and Attack Behaviors: Real-time testbeds support self-learning, AI-driven DDoS defense mechanisms that dynamically adjust to evolving attack vectors. They allow adversarial attack simulation, providing insights into how attackers modify strategies to evade detection.

Scalability and Deployment Validations: Federated testbeds facilitate cross-validation of security frameworks across different environments, ensuring detection models remain robust across diverse 5G deployments. These testbeds provide a real-world evaluation of traffic loads, congestion handling, and multi-layer security integrations, which are difficult to replicate in simulations.

H. Available Testbed Resources for Real Experiment

Several NSF-funded advanced platforms offer valuable infrastructure for experimentation and testing, offering major advantages over traditional simulation, emulation, and real

testbed environments, particularly in the context of B5G/6G research.

PAWR⁹ platforms such as ARA, POWDER, and COSMOS offer real-world wireless environments that allow researchers to experiment with and evaluate next-generation wireless technologies under operational conditions, including 5G, edge computing, and SDN. The platforms provide flexibility and reconfigurability, facilitating real-time experimentation and thorough end-to-end testing. This makes them well-suited for simulating and mitigating DDoS attacks in actual network environments.

ACCESS¹⁰ provides researchers with access to supercomputing resources, including GPUs and advanced computing systems, which are well-suited for conducting large-scale simulations of DDoS attack scenarios and exploring mitigation strategies. Chameleon¹¹ and CloudLab¹² facilitate researchers in experimenting with entirely adjustable software stacks and cloud architectures, thus enabling the development of innovative DDoS mitigation techniques in adaptable environments. FABRIC¹³ and NRP¹⁴ offer high-performance computing and networking resources that facilitate extensive, practical DDoS research, utilizing technologies such as machine learning and distributed computing. OSG¹⁵ facilitates the execution of multiple autonomous activities, hence simulating the scattered characteristics of DDoS attacks.

These platforms offer cost-effective access to advanced resources essential for DDoS mitigation research, removing the need for organizations to build and maintain costly infrastructure independently. The learning curve is also manageable, with extensive documentation, tutorials, and support from research communities, which helps researchers, even those with limited resources, quickly get started. These platforms enable users to tailor their environments without the necessity of managing physical hardware, thereby simplifying the setup process. These platforms are affordable and reduce barriers to entry, facilitating researchers in conducting advanced, large-scale experiments.

I. Testbed for B5G/6G

For B5G/6G, these 5G tools are still relevant. The 6G security testbed can be developed with advanced 5G tools and open-source projects. They support network slicing, orchestration, and virtualization, which are crucial for the dynamic and heterogeneous network environment of 6G. Extensions may be required to handle more complex scenarios and integrate additional security functions. The paper [179] uses, for example, OpenStack, Open-Source MANO (OSM),

Open5GS, FlexRAN, SNORT, Open Air Interface (OAI) and Magma for the provision and management of core network services and cybersecurity solutions. These technologies are tailored to support security analytics, such as SDN, NFV, intrusion detection, malware analysis, and the RAN, to meet the broader and more complicated requirements of 6G. However, the 6G architecture is not yet established, and there are challenges in upgrading 5G testbeds to 6G testbeds, e.g., the integration of advanced technologies such as data processing capabilities, ultra-massive MIMO antennas, THz communication, and AI-driven network functionalities.

Wang et al. [178] examine the technologies and testbeds specific to 6G in detail. According to the paper, progress has been made in the development of 6G testbeds. Purple Mountain Laboratories has built a comprehensive verification platform, "TKμ", which combines cell-free ultra-massive distributed MIMO, Reconfigurable Intelligent Surfaces (RIS)-assisted 6G wireless communications, and integrated space-to-ground communications. This platform seeks to validate key performance characteristics such as peak Tbps rates, microsecond latency, and high spectral efficiency. In addition, mmWave testbeds such as LuMaMi28 at Lund University focus on real-time massive MIMO systems with beam-switching antenna arrays. Terahertz testbeds, in particular TeraNova, enable ultra-broadband wireless communication with record-breaking data rates and spectral efficiency. RIS prototypes utilize hundreds of adjustable features to improve signal coverage and quality. OWC testbeds include light fidelity (LiFi), free space optics (FSO), and optical camera communication (OCC) technologies that demonstrate high data speeds and decentralized beam steering. Global initiatives by countries such as Finland, the United States, and China are critical to the development and standardization of these technologies. Organizations such as 3GPP and IEEE are currently working to create a uniform basis for 6G. Overall, these developments are an important step towards the technical capabilities required for 6G networks.

J. Dataset for 5G/B5G DDoS Mitigation Research

The majority of datasets commonly used in the literature, such as CICDDoS2019, CSE-CIC-IDS2018, CIC-IDS2017, UNSW-NB2015, NSL-KDD, and KDD99 [114], [115], have played a foundational role in advancing DDoS mitigation research in recent years. These resources, though often generated under controlled or partially synthetic environments, offer valuable labeled attack traffic and structured feature sets that facilitate benchmarking and algorithm development. Particularly for early-stage prototyping and comparative analysis, these datasets remain indispensable. However, as 5G and B5G networks introduce new complexities, such as ultra-reliable low-latency communications (URLLC), network slicing, and distributed MEC infrastructures, there is an increasing need for datasets that more fully capture the temporal, architectural, and protocol diversity of modern mobile ecosystems. CDR datasets from Telecom Italia from

⁹<https://advancedwireless.org/>

¹⁰<https://access-ci.org/>

¹¹<https://www.chameleoncloud.org/>

¹²<https://www.cloudlab.us/>

¹³<https://portal.fabric-testbed.net/>

¹⁴<https://nationalresearchplatform.org/>

¹⁵<https://osg-htc.org/>

literature [112] are a notable example, which reflect real mobile user behavior over time. Semi-realistic datasets such as TON-IoT [180], Edge-IIoTset [181], Bot-IoT [182], Aposemat IoT-23 [183], and MedBIoT [184] have taken significant steps toward bridging this gap by incorporating real device behavior with strategically injected attacks. While these datasets approximate real-world conditions better than earlier generations, they may still abstract away certain network-layer dynamics, such as mobility patterns, service migration across MEC, and inter-slice interference-factors that are increasingly critical in B5G contexts. Real-world traces, including the MAWI Working Group Traffic Archive¹⁶ and CAIDA DDoS Attack Dataset [185], offer anonymized backbone-scale traffic patterns and can complement these semi-synthetic resources for more rigorous evaluations. For a 5G specific scenario, [186], [187] are examples of realistic datasets. There are other resources for real data, such as this GitHub repository¹⁷ and IEEE data port¹⁸. To ensure robustness and practical relevance, we thus recommend combining these datasets with controlled, multi-vector synthetic attacks, applying cross-dataset validation, and focusing on non-stationary traffic behaviors to reflect the real-world volatility of 5G/B5G services. Additionally, dataset selection should consider varied deployment contexts-RAN, edge, and core-to support the development of comprehensive, low-latency, and self-adaptive mitigation frameworks that align with 5G's zero-touch and service-level assurance paradigms. Integrating real and hybrid datasets in this way significantly enhances the generalizability and deployment readiness of DDoS defense mechanisms for current and next-generation mobile networks.

VI. Critical Takeaways and Future Research Directions in DDoS Mitigation for 5G/6G Networks

A. Key Insights

Through a comprehensive review of the existing literature, this study has provided valuable insights. The following lessons were learned:

- 1) **AI/ML Computational Overhead:** From the literature reviewed, several advanced ML-based mitigation techniques suffer from significant computational complexity. While ML-based solutions excel in scalability for handling large data flows, their high computational demands make them less suitable for real-time DDoS mitigation. This limits the practical use of ML-based mitigation techniques in real-time situations, especially in systems with limited resources. Furthermore, low latency is essential for B5G/6G, as it can affect these complex systems. Even though these algorithms aim for extremely fast detection times, the actual implementation of advanced detection methods can lead to

delays. Therefore, it is essential for advanced ML-based studies to prioritize the consideration of time complexity.

- 2) **Scalability of DL-based Approach:** Deep learning approaches, including LSTM, RNN, and CNN-based frameworks, have proven successful in detecting complex attack patterns with high accuracy and low false positive rates. Despite their efficiency, significant computational and energy costs, as well as scalability, remain critical challenges that need to be addressed.
- 3) **Orchestration Complexity:** Orchestration techniques dynamically manage network resources to isolate and mitigate DDoS attacks while maintaining high throughput for benign users. Network slicing and similar strategies have proven effective in these scenarios. However, the complexity of dynamic resource management and scalability across different network environments remains a major challenge.
- 4) **Operational and Computational Overhead in Hybrid Approach:** The use of multiple techniques in a hybrid approach offers significant protection against DDoS attacks. However, implementing hybrid systems can increase complexity and require more resources to manage effectively. It is, therefore, important to estimate the costs of implementing a hybrid model. In addition, the practical deployment of detection and mitigation solutions requires seamless integration into the current network architecture, a factor that is particularly important in hybrid systems. Hybrid techniques must overcome the difficulty of maintaining detection accuracy while minimizing the impact on legitimate traffic. They must also effectively manage operational and computational overhead.
- 5) **Blocking Legitimate Traffic:** Most studies refer to blocking as a defense mechanism. Blocking strategies provide a straightforward approach to stopping attack traffic and are a simple and quick way to mitigate attacks. The main difficulty is to avoid inadvertently blocking legitimate traffic, which could lead to service disruptions. Scalability problems under high data traffic also require careful management and optimization.
- 6) **Limitations of Static DDoS Defense Mechanisms:** It is important to have a comprehensive discussion on the adaptability of the proposed approach to a variety of DDoS attacks. This should be included as a discussion that provides a theoretical analysis perspective, even if it is not included in the experiment.
- 7) **Limited Use of Complex and Multi-Vector Attacks:** Precise and complex attack vectors are crucial for maintaining detection efficiency, which emphasizes the need for continuous improvement of real-time detection methods. Many studies focus on simple or well-known DDoS attack types (e.g., SYN floods, UDP floods) while neglecting more sophisticated, multi-vector, or application-layer attacks. This narrow focus

¹⁶<https://mawi.wide.ad.jp/mawi/>

¹⁷<https://gist.github.com/stefanbschneider/96602bb3c8b256b90058d59f337a0e59>

¹⁸<https://ieee-dataport.org/datasets>

poses a risk to real-world applicability, as modern attackers often deploy dynamic, blended strategies to evade static or single-mode detection systems. In particular, application-layer attacks, including low-and-slow HTTP floods or encrypted request bursts, present subtle patterns that are hard to detect using traditional volume-based or feature-engineered models.

- 8) **Insufficient Explanation of Experimental Procedures:** Explaining the experimental procedure, the dataset used, the technologies employed, and the specific characteristics of the attack model used can help the research community to understand possible shortcomings of the proposed approach and experiment and thereby make improvements. Without this information, it is challenging to evaluate the validity of the results or adapt the methods for different contexts.
- 9) **Reliance on Wired Network Datasets and Synthetic Data:** A recurring issue in many of the studies surveyed [103], [111], [113] is the reliance on wired network datasets to develop ML-based solutions for 5G and beyond. While these datasets are readily available, they do not accurately represent the wireless characteristics and challenges inherent to 5G and B5G environments, such as mobility, interference, and dynamic spectrum sharing, since wired datasets are generally gathered in controlled settings. Wireless environments have extra variables such as signal fading, multipath interference, and fluctuating connection strength, which can greatly impact network performance. Wired datasets fail to address the inherent differences between wireless and wired networks, making the results less relevant for 5G/B5G contexts. Similarly, synthetic datasets or simulated DDoS attack traces are generated in controlled environments. While these methods allow for reproducibility and focused testing, they may lack the variability, noise, and unpredictability found in real-world mobile network conditions. This limitation should be clearly acknowledged when developing and testing solutions in wireless environments, and more efforts should be directed toward creating wireless-specific datasets for experiments.
- 10) **Reproducibility Challenges:** Another important finding from this review is the lack of reproducibility of many studies due to a lack of documentation or GitHub links. Reproducibility is fundamental to scientific research as it ensures that experimental results can be independently verified, validated and extended. In the field of DDoS mitigation research for 5G and future networks, reproducibility is particularly important due to the complex and dynamic nature of these systems. Many papers have failed to provide access to the tools or datasets used, significantly limiting the ability of other researchers to reproduce the results or build on the work. The challenges for reproducibility in DDoS research include the proprietary nature of the

datasets, the lack of standardized test environments and the insufficient documentation of the methods. Many studies rely on custom-built test environments or private datasets that are not publicly available, making independent validation difficult. In addition, different network configurations, traffic patterns and attack scenarios make it difficult to reproduce the results.

- 11) **Reliance on Simulations:** A critical gap in current research is the reliance on simulations rather than real-world test environments. The studies reviewed in this paper mostly use simulators/emulators. While simulations provide valuable insights, they cannot capture the full complexity and unpredictability of real networks. In contrast, physical test environments allow researchers to directly observe real-world conditions such as signal propagation, interference and hardware-specific performance, which are usually oversimplified or poorly simulated in simulators.
- 12) **Privacy and Security Concerns in DDoS Mitigation Approaches:** Privacy and security concerns, especially in federated and trust-based learning frameworks, must be taken into account to ensure privacy while maintaining high detection accuracy. Mitigation strategies that use third-party DDoS protection services, such as ML-based detection, may need the exchange of network data with external providers, giving rise to concerns regarding the storage and utilization of this data. Moreover, IDS and firewalls may unintentionally collect personal data while monitoring for malicious traffic as part of DDoS mitigation. Typically, these systems depend on DPI to distinguish between valid and malicious requests, therefore revealing the contents of communication packets and so heightening the vulnerability to privacy breaches.

B. Scope of Advancements in DDoS Mitigation Techniques

Building on the lesson learned, the future research directions for the advancements in DDoS mitigation techniques are discussed below:

- 1) **Real-Time Testbed Development for DDoS Research:** Given the availability of resources as discussed in Section H, future research should emphasize building and testing on real-time testbeds to provide more accurate results, as simulations may overlook factors such as network latency, hardware variability, and the evolving nature of DDoS threats in real environments. Real testbed environments offer a more precise depiction of network behaviors and attack dynamics, which is crucial for the advancement of scalable defense mechanisms. This shift toward real testbeds will help bridge the gap between theoretical solutions and their practical applications.

- 2) **Adversarial AI/ML/DL for Proactive DDoS Detection and Mitigation:** As attackers increasingly use adversarial ML methods to develop DDoS attacks that can evade AI/ML-based detection systems, DDoS defenses are becoming more complex. Future research should focus on leveraging the capabilities of AI, ML, and DL to enable real-time, proactive, adaptive, and autonomous DDoS detection and mitigation in these complex environments that can also process large amounts of data.
- 3) **Enhancing Speed and Scalability of ML-Based Approaches:** Expanding on the last point, exploring hardware acceleration through specialized processors like GPUs or TPUs can significantly reduce delays and lower the costs associated with deploying ML-based solutions. Cloud-native architectures present opportunities for cost-effective solutions through the efficient distribution of workloads across edge and cloud resources. Future investigations should prioritize enhancing the scalability and adaptability of ML-driven DDoS mitigation solutions so the models possess the flexibility to adjust to evolving traffic conditions and new attack vectors, particularly low-rate and stealthy threats. Investigating lightweight ML models or distributed learning techniques will be essential for minimizing computational overhead and improving scalability in future research.
- 4) **Addressing Sophisticated and Evolving DDoS Attack Vectors:** In the existing literature, various types of DDoS attacks on mobile infrastructures are studied in detail. However, there are other types of DDoS attacks that need to be further researched, including slow-loris attacks, source signaling and softening attacks, pulsing/zombie flood attacks, quantum computing-assisted attacks, network edge resource depletion attacks, and blockchain-based DDoS attacks. Future research should aim to design comprehensive detection systems capable of recognizing and adapting to multi-vector and evolving DDoS attack strategies. This includes models that can correlate signals across layers (e.g., application, transport, signaling) and dynamically respond to hybrid threat patterns.
- 5) **Exploring DDoS Mitigation Strategies in Non-Terrestrial Networks (NTN):** While 6G remains largely in the visionary research phase, it is crucial to begin exploring key technologies that will shape its development to ensure the secure evolution of these technologies, especially against DDoS. Though numerous studies exist on defense strategies against DDoS in cellular networks, emerging research opportunities and unexplored areas await investigation. One promising area for future exploration is the integration of non-terrestrial networks (NTNs), including satellites from Low Earth Orbit, Medium Earth Orbit, and Geostationary Orbit, along with high-altitude platforms, into B5G networks. Network environments offer distinct opportunities and challenges, particularly regarding DDoS attacks [88]. Creating robust DDoS mitigation strategies for deployment across diverse domains presents a significant challenge, given the varied nature of these environments. Future research must prioritize harnessing the potential of NTN and the Space-Air-Ground-Sea Integrated network to enhance the security and resilience of B5G/6G networks against DDoS attacks. In addition, blockchain technology offers a decentralized and tamper-resistant method for tracking and mitigating DDoS attacks, enhancing the security and resilience of B5G/6G networks. A thorough evaluation of the feasibility and performance of blockchain-based solutions within B5G/6G networks is crucial. Furthermore, research is scarce regarding blockchain-based solutions for mitigating DDoS attacks in mobile networks, indicating a need for deeper exploration.
- 6) **Investigating Quantum-Resistant Techniques:** Furthermore, the area of quantum-resistant security for B5G needs much more attention from researchers. As B5G/6G networks are expected to support a wide range of critical applications, the need for accurate and adaptive DDoS detection and mitigation techniques becomes paramount. Current cryptographic techniques could become vulnerable to quantum computing, which requires the development of quantum-resistant security solutions. Future research should investigate the integration of quantum-based cryptography and PQC along with QKD to safeguard B5G/6G communications against emerging quantum threats [188]. It is important to focus more on the research and implementation of post-quantum cryptographic algorithms to secure B5G networks against quantum-based DDoS attacks. The application of Quantum ML [189] should also be explored to improve the reliability and adaptability of DDoS defenses in these complex environments.
- 7) **Leveraging Multi-Access Edge Computing (MEC):** The centralized nature of traditional DDoS mitigation approaches is often unsuitable for the highly distributed and dynamic B5G/6G architectures. Future research should focus on developing distributed DDoS mitigation strategies that leverage multi-access edge computing (MEC) and edge intelligence to enable faster response times and more localized defense mechanisms.
- 8) **Scaling DDoS Detection Systems:** Another challenge is scaling the detection systems to handle the large volumes of data generated, especially by IoT devices in B5G/6G networks. The high bandwidth requirements and strict latency constraints of B5G/6G services, especially for URLLC applications, pose significant challenges to traditional DDoS mitigation techniques. Future research should investigate the potential of

Terahertz communication (THz) and Massive MIMO technologies to improve the capacity and resilience of B5G/6G systems against DDoS attacks. In a related context, advances in Massive MIMO can indirectly contribute to DDoS detection and mitigation by improving the efficiency and accuracy of the underlying algorithms. Investigating the integration of these technologies into B5G/6G DDoS mitigation frameworks can provide valuable insights.

- 9) **Privacy-Preserving Techniques:** Data privacy continues to be a critical concern. Mitigation systems inherently monitor and process substantial amounts of network traffic, potentially exposing sensitive user information. Although privacy-preserving methods are present in areas such as ML [190] and DL [191], a notable gap remains in the application of these techniques for real-time DDoS mitigation. Future research should concentrate on the development of scalable privacy-preserving algorithms tailored for high-speed, large-scale environments. This may involve employing encryption techniques or differential privacy to safeguard data while maintaining the effectiveness of attack detection.
- 10) **Integration of Dynamic Trust Metrics:** Despite the use of trust-based strategies in a few studies, the integration of dynamic trust metrics, which evolve based on real-time behavioral patterns into ML-based DDoS detection remains limited. This presents a valuable direction for future research, particularly in 5G/B5G networks where adaptability and context-awareness are critical. Trust-aware learning frameworks, such as reinforcement learning with trust-based rewards or graph neural networks with trust propagation, may offer promising solutions to this challenge.
- 11) **Improving Reproducibility in DDoS Mitigation Research:** Future research should focus on comprehensive documentation of the experimental setup, the use of public datasets and the sharing of open source tools. In cases where data sharing is not possible, anonymized or synthetic datasets should be described in detail. Standardised test environments and benchmarks should be used for consistent, comparable analyses. To provide specific recommendations for improving reproducibility, we suggest the following checklist for authors:
 - a. Dataset Accessibility:* Make sure that datasets (real or simulated) are publicly accessible or contain clear access instructions (e.g. GitHub links). Include descriptions of the datasets: source, size, features, and pre-processing steps.
 - b. Source Code and Tools:* Make comprehensive source code available via repositories (e.g. GitHub) that use version control. List dependencies, software versions, and configurations required for execution.
 - c. Experimental Setup:* Specify hardware specifications (e.g., CPU, GPU, memory) and network configurations. Explicitly describe the

- d. Parameter Settings:* Document the parameters used, such as hyperparameters, thresholds, and tuning procedures for AI/ML models. Incorporate configuration files if required.
- e. Evaluation Metrics:* Provide performance metrics (e.g. accuracy, false positive rate, latency) and their calculation methods. Provide baseline comparisons with current models or benchmarks.
- f. Documentation:* Include a comprehensive README with step-by-step instructions for replication. Describe any known limitations or discrepancies in the results.
- g. Results Reproducibility:* Provide raw data, logs, and scripts for statistical analysis to verify results. Provide scripts for generating plots and tables if necessary. Also state the Operating system used, hardware specification, configuration, seed values etc.

By following this checklist as presented in Table 16 and incorporating these guidelines, researchers can significantly improve the reproducibility of their studies and foster a more transparent and collaborative scientific community advocating for effective DDoS mitigation strategies for 5G and beyond.

TABLE 16. Reproducibility Checklist for DDoS Detection Research

Checklist Item	Description
Dataset Accessibility	Real/synthetic, with access link if available.
Source Code and Tools	Tools, libraries, or simulators used, including versions; source code links (i.e., GitHub) if public.
Experimental Setup	Testbed/simulation environment, including hardware, VMs, topology, and scenarios.
Parameter Settings	Key model parameters, and tuning info.
Evaluation Metrics	Metrics such as accuracy, F1-score, false positive rate, and latency, used to assess performance.
Documentation	All experimental procedures, feature extraction steps, and assumptions.
Result Reproducibility	System specs (CPU, RAM, OS), runtime settings, seed values, and configuration files, scripts if applicable.

VII. Conclusion

In recent years, there has been an increase in the amount of DDoS attacks directed against B5G networks. This paper has investigated a number of interesting methods for detecting and mitigating attacks, each of which has its own set of advantages and disadvantages. These attacks and the methods to detect and mitigate these attacks have been discussed in this paper. It is the hybrid approach that

combines the strengths of multiple methods, which results in a new path of DDoS mitigation while simultaneously increasing complexity. The majority of work detection and defense processes are hybrid approaches. When it comes to the implementation of these technologies, there are still prevalent challenges, such as adaptability, the requirement for resources, and the possibility of false detection. Both the attack surface and the number of devices are growing as the B5G continues to advance. Aside from the fact that AI and ML-based approaches are increasing the accuracy of detection and making defenses more effective, attackers are also employing AI and ML-based attacks. As a result, new zero-day DDoS attacks are appearing, which is creating a need for additional research in this constantly evolving field. To guide future research in DDoS detection and mitigation within 5G/B5G systems, our review highlights several promising directions that merit deeper academic exploration. These include the development of real-time, scalable testbeds to validate detection strategies under realistic traffic conditions, and the optimization of ML-based models for high-speed environments, focusing on both computational efficiency and detection latency. Furthermore, addressing multi-vector and application-layer complexities remains critical for enhancing detection robustness. Future work should also explore privacy-preserving algorithms that can operate effectively on encrypted or obfuscated data, especially in resource-constrained or high-throughput settings. Additional research is needed in areas such as NTN, quantum-resistant DDoS mitigation frameworks, MEC-assisted detection, and the establishment of reproducible benchmarks and open-source repositories to foster standardization. These directions collectively point toward the need for adaptive, context-aware, and future-proof solutions to secure next-generation mobile infrastructures.

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